

D15.2 First report of the technical integration of the EOOSC Beyond Pilot Nodes

30/09/2025

Abstract

The EOOSC Beyond Pilot Nodes are building a distributed network that combines research resources supported by the Federated Capabilities of the EOOSC Core Innovation Sandbox to create integrated research environments. Technical integration plans, guided by scientific user stories, demonstrate how researchers can benefit from this network. This work promotes best practices for broader adoption and showcases how a behind-the-scenes Pilot Nodes Network can accelerate scientific research.

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Executive Summary

One of the objectives of EOSC Beyond is to establish a set of Pilot Nodes and prototype their integration to enable use cases that leverage cross-Node services and datasets. This foundational work began with the identification of scientific needs and the development of technical integration plans within the emerging EOSC Federation. These plans were prepared in close collaboration with potential stakeholders of the Pilot Nodes, including representatives of end users and Node service providers.

The Pilot Nodes have since made substantial progress in integration. Each Node addresses challenges specific to its scientific domain while also tackling common issues that can be resolved using EOSC Core Federating Capabilities, such as AAI and Helpdesk federation. This dual approach has ensured both individual progress and collective benefit across all Pilot Nodes.

This progress results from a close collaboration between the Pilot Nodes and the product and service owners delivering EOSC Beyond's Core services. This interaction has been essential for understanding how Core services operate in a federated environment and for refining the integration plans accordingly.¹

The EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox has played a pivotal role in this process. It enables Pilot Nodes to test integrations with Core Federating Capabilities and validate them through real-world scientific user stories. Initial demonstrations have showcased several innovative implementations, including federated resource discovery and the dynamic composition of services across multiple Pilot Nodes.

Implementation of the cross-Node use cases derived from these scientific user stories has already produced compelling results:

- CESSDA and INSTRUCT-ERIC demonstrated how social scientists could discover and book structural biology instruments with SSO.
- METROFOOD-RI and CESSDA combined food composition and socio-economic data with Helpdesk mediation.
- INSTRUCT-ERIC and EGI showed how storage brokering at the point of experiment supports long-term data retention.
- NFDI, LifeWatch and EGI enabled compute close to data by staging datasets through machine-actionable DOIs.
- ENES and EGI demonstrated advanced computational and machine learning environments supported by AAI cross-node federation.
- CNB-CSIC leveraged computational resources from the e-INFRA CZ Node to simplify complex validation workflows.
- NI4OS-Europe deployed a dedicated instance of the Service Catalogue, achieving out-of-the-box interoperability with the Sandbox Service Catalogue instance.

¹ For more information on Core Services visit [EOSC Beyond Service Portfolio](#)

D15.2 First report of the technical integration of the EOSC Beyond Pilot Nodes

In the second part of the project, efforts will focus on further enhancing Pilot Nodes as users' main entry point for executing cross-Node use cases and on extending the set of supported user stories with new integrations.

1. Introduction

This report provides evidence for a "science first" approach to establish a network of Pilot EOSC Nodes. Scientific stories from real users, triggering cross-Node use cases, have been at the forefront of all the technical integration activities to demonstrate the added-value of a Node-based EOSC Federation. These cross-Node use cases leverage scientific resources and generic services from various pilots and the set of Core Federating Capabilities delivered by the EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox, acting as Federator, in alignment with the EOSC Platform Architecture and Network of EOSC Nodes described in **EOSC Beyond D5.3**.

The network of Pilot Nodes serves a dual purpose:

- offer a pre-operational environment for digital infrastructures wishing to establish an EOSC Node to experiment with and validate the integrations needed for their service offerings.
- demonstrate how enabling cross-Node use cases allows scientists to perform advanced research across disciplines.

This document aims to highlight the challenges and present solutions to elevate scientific research through the implementation of a Node-based EOSC Federation. The results presented in this deliverable can be used by those intending to perform similar technical pilot activities with the objective to develop success stories for the wider EOSC Federation.

1.1. Structure of the document

The document is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 2:** Presents the methodology adopted to establish the Pilot Nodes and define and implement the Cross-Node use cases.
- **Chapter 3:** Present the work carried out for each Pilot Node. It describes the scientific user stories, integration status and technical challenges.
- **Chapter 4:** Summarizes the feedback from the Pilot Nodes and the common challenges they faced in the WP activities.
- **Chapter 5:** Provides conclusions and highlights the activities planned for the second phase of the project.

1.2. Definitions

Definition	Description
EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox	The EOSC Beyond Innovation Sandbox is a pre-production environment where researchers, service providers, and node operators can test and integrate the latest EOSC Core

	developments in a safe, controlled setting. It acts as a Federator Node for project pilots, offering Core Federating Capabilities
Resources	Services, catalogues, digital research objects (e.g. data, software), training resources, infrastructure services and other assets that may be available in an EOSC Node and offered in the EOSC Federation.
Resource Provider	An organisation making a Resource available.
EOSC Resource Provider	An organisation making a Resource available to the EOSC Federation through the onboarding in an EOSC Node.
EOSC Node Architecture	A reference architecture that can be implemented by each Node of the Federation for the operation of their services and resources
EOSC Node	An entity complying with the EOSC Federation policies and legal framework, working at the local, national, regional, thematic or European level. An EOSC Node offers added value resources to the EOSC Federation and delivers federating capabilities in collaboration with other EOSC Nodes. Each EOSC Node has its autonomy, its own governance model and an offer in terms of resources. It operates its own platform, complying with the technical framework, and the EOSC Federation Platform architecture.
EOSC Beyond Pilot Federation	The network of Pilot Nodes created by the project.
Onboarding Resources in an EOSC Node:	Onboarding a resource in an EOSC Node means making it available to users through that Node. The provider selects one or more Nodes that best fit the resource, depending on its characteristics. For instance, if a provider manages a domain-specific data repository, they might choose a thematic Node that best represents and supports that domain.
EOSC Thematic Node	Digital infrastructure specialised for a specific scientific domain of research or with specific techniques.
EOSC National/Regional Nodes	An EOSC Node for a regional or national community
EOSC Federating Capabilities	EOSC Federating Capabilities are the added-value capabilities offered by the EOSC Federation that allow all EOSC end-users and providers to exploit services, data and other resources in the Federation.

Node Core functions	The Node Core functions enable the basic operation of an EOSC Node. An initial reference implementation of these Node Core functions has been implemented by the EOSC EU Node. The Node Core functions can be implemented by an EOSC Node as functions of a platform, individual services, or acquired through the EOSC Federation (offered as-a-Service or using the technology of the reference implementation).
Node Resources	Services, data and other research products, usually listed in a catalogue, that end-users of this Node can access directly.
Node Exchange services	Services and other resources a Node shares with the EOSC Federation. They contribute to the collective EOSC Exchange.

Table 1: Definitions²

² The definitions in this table referring to the EOSC Nodes have been applied in this document in the context of a Pilot Node.

2. Methodology

2.1. The overall approach to technical integration

EOSC Beyond applies an agile, iterative approach to the technical integration of EOSC Pilot Nodes into a federated ecosystem. The integration is grounded in real user needs and driven by concrete scientific use cases developed by the Pilot Nodes.

The process starts with the definition of scientific user stories by each Pilot Node. These stories serve as the basis for identifying required services, integration types, and technical dependencies. A continuous feedback loop is maintained between Pilot Nodes, technical teams, and EOSC Core developers to continuously refine integration plans and implementations.

Key to this methodology is the use of the EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox—a pre-production environment enabling Pilot Nodes to test service interactions and verify compliance with federation-level interoperability requirements. EOSC Beyond supports integration both between the EOSC Core and Exchange services, and among the Pilot Nodes themselves, where multiple Nodes coordinate their services to enable cross-Node workflows and deliver added scientific value to research communities.

2.2. Workshop-based co-design and feedback

The co-design methodology relies on structured stakeholder engagement, centred around collaborative workshops and shared documentation templates.

As part of this approach, the second round of the Kraków workshop, held in March 2025, focused on an in-depth technical analysis of Pilot Nodes' use cases and user stories. The primary objective was to address key challenges related to resource interoperability and service composability within the EOSC. The workshop was attended by all EOSC Pilot Nodes and representatives from the EOSC Core (WP7-8).

During the workshop, participants worked collaboratively to define technical requirements, assess relevant standards, and outline the conditions necessary to develop proof-of-concept implementations.

Objectives:

- Explore technical requirements and standards to enable interoperability across distributed resources.
- Develop a proof of concept for integrating diverse services into a unified, functional environment.
- Strengthen federated discovery and access mechanisms to enhance user engagement.
- Align implementation strategies for scalable, cross-node collaboration.

Key activities:

- **Scientific user story** - each Pilot Node identified and presented scientific user stories (one or two per node) to be implemented as part of the Sandbox integration activities. These user stories are based on real scientific workflows and community needs.
- **User Story Technical Analysis** - Pilot and technical teams collaboratively completed a structured technical breakdown of each user story to cover service dependencies, integration mechanisms, required interfaces, and preliminary security and authentication needs.
- **Core service requirement gathering** - each Pilot Node updated their requirements, identifying technical needs, service gaps, and dependencies on EOSC Core components. This has served as a direct input to WP7 and WP8, which are in charge of designing the evolution of the core services. Main outcomes and discussions with the core teams are presented in **D7.2 Final Core Gap Analysis and Requirements Report**.
- **EOSC federation discovery journey mapping from the provider perspective** - participants mapped the full onboarding and integration journey from the perspective of a service provider, highlighting key phases, touchpoints, and potential friction points.
- **EOSC federation discovery journey mapping from the user perspective** - the user-side journey was similarly mapped, capturing the researcher's perspective when accessing and composing services across the federation. This helped clarify usability expectations and necessary support structures.
- **Integration roadmap** - Pilot Nodes provided their integration schedule and dependencies in a shared roadmap. This has enabled better coordination of efforts across work packages and identification of common challenges.
- **Technical Coordinator assignment** - for each selected user story, a dedicated technical coordinator was appointed to guide the integration work, liaise with Core developers, and support interaction with WP8 teams, who lead the developments of the core services.

Key outputs from the Workshop:

1. **User story technical analysis** - documented the technical steps needed to implement the selected user story. Standardised tool for identifying required integrations, classifying integration types (e.g., API-based, workflow orchestration), and capturing security, data transformation, and interoperability needs.
2. **Core service requirement sheet** - aggregated inputs from all Pilot Nodes on service gaps, missing capabilities, and expectations toward the EOSC Core.
3. **EOSC federation discovery journey map: provider perspective** - mapped provider-side onboarding, integration touchpoints, and composability expectations.
4. **EOSC federation discovery journey map: user perspective** - captured end-user actions, goals, and pain points across the journey, from discovery to post-use.
5. **Integration roadmap** - integration timelines and dependencies in a shared document.

Figure 1: Cyclic feedback loop³

³ The figure displays a cyclic feedback loop to the development of the Pilot Federation.

3. Pilot Nodes technical integration

Each section below highlights the work done for each Pilot Node. First, a Node profile and integration goals outline the Node's scientific community, infrastructure, and EOSC-related objectives. Next, scientific user stories illustrate practical research scenarios that demonstrate how federated services are applied to solve real-world challenges. These are followed by use and feedback of Core services, where integration status, lessons learned, and additional requirements are reported. Then, the service offering of the Pilot Node is presented. Each section also discusses cross-node integration and federation aspects, showcasing collaboration with other nodes, and concludes with technical implementation details, summarising progress, encountered challenges, and solutions. This structure ensures a clear, comparable view across nodes, while capturing both the scientific and technical dimensions of the pilots.

3.1. CESSDA

CESSDA's goals are to demonstrate a number of scientific user stories that are of interest to the social sciences community and to evaluate various EOSC Core services with a view to adopting some of them post-project.

The two scientific user stories detailed below use a subset of the EOSC Core services that have been integrated to date with the CESSDA Pilot Node, and a subset of the Exchange services offered by the CESSDA Pilot Node or integrated from other Pilot Nodes. Future scientific user stories will make use of different subsets of the services available to the CESSDA Pilot Node.

3.1.1. Node Profile and integration goals

The CESSDA Pilot Node represents a specialised implementation within EOSC Beyond, designed to address the challenges and opportunities associated with Social Science data management and accessibility.

Operating as a virtual entity, it employs an innovative integration strategy that combines existing CESSDA services with the newly developed Core capabilities of EOSC Beyond and already established EOSC Core services. This hybrid approach introduces advanced functionalities that enhance data discoverability, accessibility, and interoperability across different research contexts and institutional boundaries.

The virtual nature of the CESSDA Pilot Node enables it to leverage distributed resources efficiently while presenting users with a unified interface for accessing Social Science data and related services as well as resources made available by other Nodes in the network. This architecture supports scientific user stories where researchers need to combine resources (data, compute, storage etc.) from multiple sources and collaborate with colleagues across different institutions and countries.

The EOSC-related goals are to show that a wide range of Core services can be easily integrated by a Pilot Node (and to provide feedback where this is not the case), and that CESSDA's (exchange) services can be made visible and available to a wider audience federating the Pilot Nodes' service catalogues.

3.1.2. Scientific user stories

Title: Find an instrument used in similar research studies (CESSDA-SUS-1)

Description: As a Researcher (social scientist) I want to use the same instrument for my research that was used in other similar research projects to be able to more easily compare data later.

Researcher perspective:

- Search the EOSC Discovery Hub to find similar research projects to the one they are planning.
- Select two or three studies that are similar to their project and look at the instruments that were used.
- Search the EOSC Discovery Hub to find the instruments that were used by the other projects and their location.
- Apply to the Node that holds the instruments (INSTRUCT-ERIC) for available times access to them.
- Access the instruments and carry out the relevant parts of their research.

Related Nodes: INSTRUCT-ERIC, EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox

EOSC Core Services: AAI, Service Catalogue, EOSC Discovery Hub

Exchange Services: CESSDA Data Catalogue, INSTRUCT-ERIC ARIA.

Figure 2: CESSDA-SUS-1 flow diagram

Title: Find and use data on women's political behaviour (CESSDA-SUS-2)

Description: As a Researcher (social scientist) I need data on women's political behaviour in Greece.

Researcher perspective:

- Search the federated EOSC Discovery Hub to try to find the data.
- Find some study descriptions in the federated CESSDA Data Catalogue and select the studies of interest.
- Following the link to the data publisher (**SoDaNet** Data Catalogue) to access the data.
- Download the Open data (if any) and apply for access to the restricted data, using their existing credentials, as the SoDaNet Data Catalogue is federated to the EOSC AAI, via the CESSDA IdP.
- Download the restricted data and carry out the relevant parts of their research.

Related Nodes: EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox.

EOSC Core Services: AAI, Service Catalogue, EOSC Discovery Hub

Exchange Services: CESSDA Data Catalogue, SoDaNet Data Catalogue.

Figure 3: CESSDA-SUS-2 flow diagram

3.1.3. Use and feedback of core services

AAI

Integration status: Done.

Feedback: Integration was very straightforward, as the Service Owner did most of the work, including creating and hosting an instance of an Identity Provider (IdP) for CESSDA's sole use. CESSDA had to configure the IdP to communicate with some of its own services, but the federation with other nodes was handled by the Service Owner.

Lessons learned: This is a test case for whether or not CESSDA should install and manage (or procure) an IdP after the end of the project, as it is not clear at present if there is enough demand within to warrant it. At present, it is too early to say either way.

Helpdesk

Integration status: Done.

Feedback: Integration was very straightforward, as the Service Owner did most of the work, including creating a proxy to enable two-way integration between the CESSDA Helpdesk instance and both the Metrofood's and Sandbox Helpdesk instances.

Lessons learned: Until there is a critical mass of CESSDA Exchange service users, the utility of two-way Helpdesk integration is hard to assess.

Monitoring

Integration status: Done.

Feedback: Integration was very straightforward, as the Service Owner did most of the work. CESSDA only had to provide the URLs of the endpoints to be monitored.

Additional requirements: Alerting when an endpoint becomes unavailable/re-available.

Lessons learned: CESSDA was already aware of the utility of service availability and reliability monitoring, as it had evaluated some alternative monitoring technologies prior to the start of this project.

EOSC Discovery Hub

<p>Integration status: Done.</p> <p>Feedback: Proficiency in configuring, deploying and orchestrating containerised components is required in order to use this service. There are still some bugs and missing features, which are being addressed via a dedicated issue tracker and discussions with the Service Owner and are expected to be resolved early in the next period.</p> <p>Additional requirements: The ability to customise the look and feel via an administrative UI.</p> <p>Lessons learned: Because the integration of the EOSC Discovery Hub instances was not in place when the CESSDA instance was installed and configured, the CESSDA Exchange Services had to be onboarded again. In future, a Service will only need to be onboarded once for it to be available in all relevant Nodes.</p>
<p>Service Catalogue</p>
<p>Integration status: In progress.</p> <p>Feedback: Too early to say, as installation and configuration has yet to take place.</p> <p>Additional requirements: To be updated, after integration and usage.</p> <p>Lessons learned: To be updated, after integration and usage.</p>
<p>PID Service</p>
<p>Integration status: In progress.</p> <p>Feedback: There are choices to be made as to how to use the PID Service in practice - it looks as though adopting the wrong approach could be very time consuming to address post-implementation.</p> <p>Additional requirements: To be updated, after integration and usage.</p> <p>Lessons learned: To be updated, after integration and usage.</p>
<p>Research Product Catalogue</p>
<p>Integration status: In progress.</p> <p>Feedback: Development is required both on the part of the RPC Service Owner and either the EOSC Discovery Hub Service Owner or the Service Catalogue Service Owner in order to harvest CESSDA's resources from the Research Product Catalogue.</p> <p>Additional requirements: To be updated, after integration and usage.</p> <p>Lessons learned: To be updated, after integration and usage.</p>

Table 2: CESSDA use of core services

3.1.4. CESSDA Pilot Node Exchange services

CESSDA Data Catalogue

The CESSDA Data Catalogue (CDC) used in CESSDA-SUS-2, contains descriptions (metadata) of the more than 40,000 data collections held by CESSDA's Service Providers (SPs). Data sets come from over 20 European countries. More information and a link to the service can be found at <https://www.cessda.eu/Tools/Data-Catalogue>.

Its metadata content is obtained by periodically harvesting the CESSDA Service Providers' own data catalogues via OAI-PMH.

CDC provides both a **REST API** and an OAI-PMH interface. The former returns data in JSON format, the latter provides a number of format options, the most important being DDI Codebook XML. Its contents are harvested by a number of aggregators, including the OpenAIRE Graph, BASE and GoTriple.

CESSDA Vocabulary Service

The CESSDA Vocabulary Service enables users to discover, browse, and download controlled vocabularies in a variety of languages. Vocabularies, in selected languages, can be downloaded in SKOS, HTML and PDF formats. More information and a link to the service can be found at <https://www.cessda.eu/Tools/Vocabulary-Service>.

The service also contains an Editor, where authorised users create, manage and translate the vocabularies. Access rights to the Editor are granted by the user management team. The tool can also be used for in-house vocabularies of other agencies.

The Vocabulary Service provides a **REST API** that returns data in JSON format.

SoDaNet Data Catalogue

The SoDaNet Data Catalogue, used in CESSDA-SUS-2, is provided and managed by SoDaNet, CESSDA's Service Provider for Greece. It contains eight different categories of data, namely:

- Quantitative studies
- Qualitative studies
- Mixed studies
- Cubes
- Indices & classifications
- Metadata of statistical surveys
- Corpora
- Replication data for quantitative analysis

It is available from <https://sodanet.gr/data-services/data-catalogue> and has an OAI-PMH interface.

ELSST

The European Language Social Science Thesaurus (ELSST) is a broad-based, multilingual thesaurus for the social sciences. It is owned and published by CESSDA and its national Service Providers. More information and a link to the service can be found at <https://www.cessda.eu/Tools/ELSST-Thesaurus>. ELSST provides a **REST API** that returns data in JSON format.

CESSDA Data Archiving Guide

The Data Archiving Guide (DAG) is designed to support the work of employees of data repositories by providing a general understanding of the full range of activities a data repository performs. Although the DAG was developed for and by employees of social science data archives, a lot of information applies to other archives as well and is equally useful for archiving professionals from other disciplines. More information and a link to the service can be found at <https://www.cessda.eu/Training/DAG>.

CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide

The CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide (DMEG) aims to put social scientists at the heart of making their research data FAIR. In addition, the associated **Train-the-Trainer materials** are designed to support people who conduct training courses in research data management and refer to selected resources, presentations and guidelines for preparing and conducting their own training courses. More information and a link to the service can be found [here](#).

Table 3: CESSDA Exchange services

3.1.5. Cross-node integration and federation aspects

CESSDA-SUS-1 relies on INSTRUCT-ERIC's ARIA (Access to Research Infrastructure Administration), a collection of cloud services provided by Instruct to research infrastructures, facilities and user communities within a range of scientific fields. ARIA can be set up and tailored to your exact needs within a few hours. More information and links to the constituent services can be found at <https://instruct-eric.org/help/about-aria>.

ARIA service has been federated between the Pilot Nodes and the Sandbox. As a result, researchers can find the same instrument for their research that was used in other similar research projects, which allows them to more easily compare data later. The EOSC Beyond federated AAI allows users to log in to ARIA using Single Sign On (SSO) and book a slot to use the chosen instrument (which is managed by INSTRUCT-ERIC) as part of their research. This is of benefit to researchers, as they can find the instruments of their choice via any Node in the network and apply for access via SSO, and for INSTRUCT-ERIC as it makes their services available to a wider audience.

CESSDA-SUS-2 relies on the CESSDA Data Catalogue being federated between the Pilot Nodes and the Sandbox. As a result, researchers can find studies on Political and Social Radicalism in Greece from several locations. These all point back to the SoDaNet Data

Catalogue, via CDC and access to any restricted data is facilitated via SSO. The SoDaNet Data Catalogue is linked to the CESSDA IdP, which in turn is part of the EOSC Beyond federated AAI, hence community members gain SSO access to the data files. This is of benefit to researchers, as they can find the study descriptions and associated data via any Node in the network and for CESSDA/SoDaNet as it makes their services available to a wider audience.

3.1.6. Technical implementation status, challenges and solutions

The scientific user stories (CESSDA-SUS-1 and CESSDA-SUS-2) described above enable researchers to find and access (using SSO) restricted resources from the Sandbox and any Pilot Node. This relies mostly on federating the contents of the various Nodes' Service Catalogues and the community AAI to make data studies and research instruments findable, accessible and reusable.

However, other Core Services (as listed) have been or are in the process of being integrated with the CESSDA Pilot Node, which bring further immediate benefits for CESSDA and its research community and will enable additional scientific user stories to be implemented in the next phase of the project.

The key technical tasks completed in M18 fall into two categories - those performed by the respective Service Owners and those undertaken by CESSDA. In the case of AAI, Helpdesk and Service Monitoring, the Service Owners performed the bulk of the integration work. CESSDA installed and configured an instance of the EOSC Discovery Hub and is investigating doing the same for the Service Catalogue and configured the CESSDA IdP (hosted by the Service Provider) to make the SoDaNet Data Catalogue accessible to the EOSC Beyond community via SSO.

The scientific user stories were completed by M18 and additional scientific user stories that showcase other Core and Exchange Services will be drawn up and implemented in the next phase.

To date, only minor problems have been encountered with the Core Services, relating to bugs, missing features and incomplete documentation. Feedback is provided to ensure these issues are addressed over time.

In summary, six EOSC Core services were integrated with the CESSDA Pilot Node (AAI, Helpdesk, Monitoring, EOSC Discovery Hub, Service Catalogue) by M18, with the PID Service and Research Product Catalogue expected to follow early in the next period. CESSDA Pilot Node offers five Exchange services (CESSDA Data Catalogue), CESSDA Vocabulary Service, CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide, CESSDA European Language Social Science Thesaurus and CESSDA Data Archiving Guide) by M18 and created two scientific user stories. More scientific user stories, using different combinations of integrated and onboarded services will be added in the next period.

3.2. CNB-CSIC

3.2.1. Node Profile and integration goals

The CNB-CSIC Pilot Node serves as a specialised setup within the EOSC Beyond framework, established to respond to the challenges and possibilities linked to the Structural Biology community, more precisely, those related to cryo-electron microscopy (cryo-EM) data validation in terms of quality.

Throughout the cryo-EM data cycle, numerous steps involve data generation, beginning with sample preparation and acquisition at the cryo-EM facilities and culminating in the reconstruction of the volume map and atomic models that represent the nature of a macromolecule target. As the number of maps deposited in public databases determined by cryo-EM is quickly growing, it becomes crucial to complement cryo-EM data with quality-related data at the latest stage of the cryo-EM data cycle. Indeed, not all data have the same quality, although it is not easily discernible.

In this context, by integrating CNB-CSIC's existing software with the functionalities provided through various EOSC Core and Exchange services, either enhanced or newly developed under the EOSC Beyond umbrella, the cryo-EM Validation Report Service (VRS) will be offered to the structural biology community. This consists of a modular and open validation grading system that qualifies a structure map at six different levels depending on the information available to assess it. With this, users could upload and validate their data via an open-access website, where an automated **Scipion** workflow will handle the data analysis. This service eliminates the need for users to download datasets, install software or set up the environment. A comprehensive PDF report summarising the evaluation will be available for download (CNB-CSIC-SUS-1).

Beside this and to further enhance research reliability, CNB-CSIC will use the VRS to analyse all the structures deposited in major repositories such as the Electron Microscopy Data Bank (EMDB) and the Protein Data Bank (PDB). These validated research outputs will be accessible through a public repository, which can populate any EOSC catalogue such as the EOSC Research Product Catalogue or the EOSC User Space (CNB-CSIC-SUS-2).

This aligns with different EOSC-related goals, since with this integrated approach researchers in structural biology can easily access cryo-EM validation tools without requiring local computing power, storage resources, or to set up the required infrastructure (CNB-CSIC-SUS-1) and enhance data discoverability, accessibility, and interoperability (CNB-CSIC-SUS-2).

3.2.2. Scientific user stories

CNB-CSIC-SUS-1: Validating cryo-EM maps and models in EOSC

The first scientific user story being implemented is the one related to the validation of the structural biology researcher's private data. This story involves the INSTRUCT-ERIC Pilot Node, in the way that the researcher could start the data cycle by submitting a

proposal to ARIA, the INSTRUCT's access and data management platform, in order to analyse a target macromolecule structure. If the proposal is accepted, a time slot would be assigned to this user at the facility. Upon processing the acquired data and obtaining a cryo-EM map along with an atomic model, the researcher will seek to validate the data to assess its quality.

In order to do so, the researcher would look for validation software in the Resource Catalogue and will find the VRS and access the current website (<https://biocomp.cnb.csic.es/EMValidationService/>).

There, and after login, the researcher will upload the data and, once finished, a VRS instance will be deployed in the cloud through the Execution Framework (EOSC Deployment Service) after requesting access to this service using the Order Management Core service. The previous data, which mainly consists of the cryo-EM volume map, the atomic model and other important parameters such as the voxel size or the estimated resolution, will be transferred to this instance using the Data Transfer exchange service.

As a result, a validation report with a DOI associated (obtained using the PIDs core service) will be generated. If the structural biology researcher is happy enough with the quality obtained, they will publish the cryo-EM map and atomic model at EMDDB and PDB respectively. If not, the researcher will optimise the processing workflow and use this service as many times as needed.

Figure 4: CNB-CSIC-SUS-1 flow diagram

3.2.3. Use and feedback of core services

AAI
<p>Status: In progress</p> <p>The integration of the AAI with the website https://biocomp.cnb.csic.es/EMValidationService/ is still in progress. The domain cnb-csic-proxy.pilot.eosc-beyond.eu has been set up to host the node's Infrastructure Proxy and a Community AAI, deployed using the RCIAM Keycloak solution. Once the AAI integration is completed, CNB-CSIC will integrate with the User Space and the Order Management core services.</p>
EOSC Deployment Service
<p>Status: Done</p> <p>CNB-CSIC has achieved with success the deployment of the VRS software properly set up using the EOSC Deployment Service, more specifically the Infrastructure Manager tool (IM) which is behind it. This deployment was tested in different architectures: with a single machine at IISAS cloud and in a cluster (consisting of one master and one worker) in CESNET cloud. There we were able to run several data validations without any issues.</p>

Table 4: CNB-CSIC use of core services

3.2.4. CNB-CSIC Pilot Node Exchange services

The Validation Report Service
<p>The outcome of the implementation of CNB-CSIC-SUS-1 will be the availability of the Validation Report Service – a set of image processing tools for validating CryoEM maps by assessing the consistency between the reconstructed map and the experimental data used to generate it – to the structural biology EOSC community.</p>
The Validation Report Service public catalogue
<p>Apart from the validation of private user data, and with the implementation of CNB-CSIC-SUS-2, the existing public data published in the Electron Microscopy Data Bank (EMDB) and the Protein Data Bank (PDB) will be analysed using the Validation Report Service. The resulting reports will be made available to any structural biologist interested in exploring additional quality validation methods beyond those already offered by the public databases.</p>

Table 5: CNB-CSIC Exchange services

3.2.5. Cross-node integration and federation aspects

As it is described in the previous sections, the **Compute and Storage exchange** services are currently being used, with CESNET being the provider of both of them.

When the AAI and the Order Management Core services are fully integrated, the **Data Transfer** exchange service will be used for transferring the structural biology researcher private data to the machine/s deployed at CESNET. And, accordingly, the Validation Report Service itself, which will also be an exchange service.

CNB-CSIC is closely linked with INSTRUCT-ERIC. The latter, as a pan-European distributed research infrastructure making high-end technologies and methods in structural biology available to users, comprises 17 Member Countries and Organisations, one of them being the CNB-CSIC, which offers services related to 3D structural analysis using electron microscopy methods.

As a result of the combination of INSTRUCT-ERIC and CNB-CSIC, these Pilot Nodes will perfectly represent the whole data cycle for cryo-EM data, from sample preparation and acquisition to the reconstruction of volume maps and atomic models, ensuring that quality-related data is integrated.

A proper way to federate both of them would be ensuring AAI interoperability. That is, an INSTRUCT-ERIC user could login at <https://biocomp.cnb.csic.es/EMValidationService/> using their ARIA credentials and submit the density map and atomic model obtained after processing the cryo-EM raw data (movies or micrographs) obtained at a INSTRUCT-ERIC electron microscopy facility and finally launch a VRS validation in a clear and straightforward manner.

Moreover, CNB-CSIC is integrated with the EGI Cloud Compute service, enabling the deployment of the VRS through the Deployment Service and the use of its computing resources.

3.2.6. Technical implementation status, challenges and solutions

The VRS compute software is fully containerized at <https://github.com/I2PC/scipion-containers/> and the infrastructure needed can be deployed successfully with the Infrastructure Manager. We faced some problems related to computing infrastructure availability in CESNET, however they were easily managed and solved by the CESNET team.

The plan for the second period is to have the VRS service fully integrated with AAI, User Space and Order Management and hopefully with the Helpdesk, Monitoring and PID core service too.

If time allows it, CNB-CSIC would like to implement the second scientific story, which consists of exposing current **EMDB VRS validations** as a catalogue in EOSC.

Therefore, phase 1 (months 1 to 18) of the CNB-CSIC Pilot has succeeded because the VRS can be programmatically deployed in a cloud provider. In phase 2 (months 19 to 36)

the whole CNB-CSIC-SUS1 should be accomplished and hopefully the CNB-CSIC-SUS2 too.

3.3. EGI Pilot Node

3.3.1. Node Profile and integration goals

The EGI Node, legally represented by the EGI Foundation, is an e-Infrastructure comprising 27 members of the EGI Federation, including national compute/storage providers, providers of generic computational platforms, and providers of thematic applications. It supports all scientific disciplines, offering computing and data analytic services to help scientists and research organisations to advance science and innovate.

EGI Pilot Node **service portfolio** consists of an operational set of services that include amongst others cloud and high-throughput compute, cloud container compute, software distribution and orchestration, workload managers for distributed environments, notebooks environments and data transfer and storage. This offer is complemented by a set of core federating capabilities that allow the management and operation of the EGI Federation including an AARC and EOSC-Compliant AAI service.

The main EOSC-related goals in EOSC Beyond include contributing to dedicated capacity for transnational and cross-disciplinary access to services and tools operated within other EOSC Nodes and supporting international use cases directly served by the EGI Node. This capacity will be provided by selected compute-data centres of the EGI Federation.

A successful EGI Pilot Node will showcase how EGI's federated infrastructure and services are effectively integrated with EOSC Beyond Core services, enabling seamless access to computational and storage resources for cross-border and cross-disciplinary research.

3.3.2. Scientific user stories

Researchers from existing scientific communities or Research Infrastructures make use of community portals or RI dedicated services to address community specific needs. However, the infrastructure needed to carry out advanced research may not always exist or be customised to fulfil the needs of each individual set of requirements.

EGI Pilot Node enables scientists from the EOSC Beyond Pilot Nodes to deploy customised infrastructure and to orchestrate together services, datasets and the adequate set of computing and storage resources.

Scientists usually start their journey in their own community catalogues and identify a dataset or service of interest. They need to follow up their journeys with the discovery of compute, storage or a virtual research environment where they can perform their research. The following use stories illustrate real deployments that have been enabled across Pilots.

EGI-SUS-1: Customised infra for data analysis

As a Researcher I want to use compute resources that allow me to run analysis services for further postprocessing, validation and publication.

Researcher perspective:

- The scientist identifies a dataset of interest in their community portal.
- EOSC Discovery Hub allows them to find EGI Cloud compute.
- EOSC Order Management will allow the user to customise the Cloud Compute requirements.
- EOSC AAI allows the user to login with EGI Check-in in order to proceed with order.
- EOSC Deployment service allows the configuration of a custom template that brings together datasets/services and the choice of compute together with a virtual research environment where he can execute directly the community resources.

Related Nodes: EGI, LifeWatch, NFDI, EOSC Sandbox

EOSC Services: AAI, Service Catalogue, Discovery Hub, Deployment Service, Order Management

Exchange Services: EGI Cloud Compute

EGI-SUS-2: Virtualised storage and data publication

As a Research Infrastructure facility, I want storage capacity so that researchers can postprocess data from experiments and publish additional results

Researcher perspective:

- The scientist needs an online storage facility to perform further analysis after data collection from the facility at RI.
- The user searches the Discovery Hub and discovers DataHub.
- EOSC AAI allows the user to login with EGI Check-in in order to proceed with order.
- The ordering system will trigger a support request at EGI Helpdesk to set up a virtual space with dedicated virtual storage providers.
- The user can make use of the command line DataHub OneData client, or Instruct FandanGO/ARIA to make their storage available to the designated virtualised storage.
- Files can receive DOIs and metadata can be entered into the system and ready for publication at the Research Products Catalogue (following OAI guidelines)

Related Nodes: EGI, INSTRUCT, EOSC Sandbox

EOSC Services: AAI, Service Catalogue, Discovery Hub, Research Products Catalogue

Exchange Services: EGI DataHub

3.3.3. Use and feedback of core services

AAI

Status of Integration: Done

Feedback: EGI Check-in follows an AARC Blueprint Architecture (**AARC-BPA**) in compliance with **EOSC AAI architecture**. Its proxy component allows other community AAI to provide access to the EGI services. Equally EGI users can have access to the Sandbox environment services through dedicated Proxy agreement. Pilot nodes such as ENES and CNB-CSIC, are using EGI Check-in as their Community AAI, enabling their users to manage their identities, groups, and roles for authorisation to their services. The AAI is a key core service to establish any interaction with other services as well as for end users from other Nodes.

Additional Requirements: Initial integrations have focused on bilateral proxies' integration. Further set ups would benefit from "an integrate once" approach with the EOSC AAI federation HUB providing access to all other EOSC compliant Pilot nodes. While this approach may simplify the number of integrations to be established it may also create a central dependency. A combined approach where several federators operate in the network could also be explored. This can be achieved by leveraging **OpenID Federation**. Support for OpenID Federation across different AAI software stacks used by several of the Pilot Nodes is currently being developed by WP8. While OpenID Federation reduces the need for multiple bilateral integrations by enabling trust to be established through signed entity configurations and trust chains, central dependencies remain on entities acting as Trust Anchors (providing the root of trust) and Intermediates (federation operators or aggregators within the trust chain).

Lessons Learned: Understanding of access policies and entitlements to map from Pilot Nodes entitlements to local entitlements is still a complex and manual process. EOSC access policies and the corresponding entitlements should be defined for generic types of access that can be easily recognised and automatically mapped to local ones.

Service Catalogue

Status of Integration: In progress

Feedback: EGI has onboarded all its services to the Sandbox Service Catalogue. This process has been done through the service onboarding portal manually. In the next phase a Service Catalogue instance together with a White Label Market Place solution will be installed to test the service synchronization in an automated manner.

Additional requirements: Federation of services should be made available so discoverability and composability of multi-node resources is possible from a single-entry point.

Lessons learnt: Discoverability of services from the Pilot network is still done either via Sandbox instance or the dedicated Pilot service catalogues. A fully federated solution where Pilots have the possibility to discover selective resources from other Nodes in the Pilot network will expand the capabilities of the network as a whole and ease some of the cross-node deployments.

Order management

Status: To be done

Feedback: In the next phase service parametrisation will be performed via integration with the order management Core service. This will allow connecting the EGI Helpdesk to the ordering system to support the integrations and ensure capacity requirements meet the expectations and needs of the users.

Additional requirements: The provision of infrastructure resources such as cloud compute and storage may still involve some human negotiations to instantiate the right level of resources. Resource provision would benefit from an automatic handling of infrastructure requirements across the federation.

Deployment Service

Status of Integration: Done

Feedback: e-Infrastructure services can easily be instantiated thanks to the Deployment Service. This service is key to bringing resources across the Pilot Network together in standardised and properly configured deployments.

Additional requirements: The integration of the deployment service with some of the front ends such as the Ordering Service or the Research Products Catalogue would ease the flow from discovery, order, deployment and usage of scientific resources and services.

Lessons Learnt: The deployment service allows for a powerful combination, integrating e-infrastructure services alongside domain-specific resources from thematic or national nodes to provide collocated data and compute solutions for today's complex AI and analytical environments in scientific research.

Helpdesk

Integration status: In progress

Feedback: EGI Pilot Node is running a Zammad instance for the **Helpdesk**. During the second part of the project the EGI Helpdesk will be integrated with the EOSC Ordering Management system to support all the service orders and escalate tickets to EOSC Sandbox Helpdesk when relevant.

Table 6: EGI use of core services

3.3.4. EGI Pilot Node exchange services

EGI has made available its whole set of e-infrastructure services to the EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox. These are available through the **Discovery Hub**. All the exchange services are integrated with EGI Check-in, so access is provided in compliance with EOSC AAI architecture. In particular, the services that have contributed to the user stories are:

- **EGI Cloud Compute**: offers on demand Virtual Machines customised to the needs of researchers.
- **EGI DataHub**: offers a virtualised access to distributed file-based storage.
- **EGI Notebooks**: offers a virtual research environment powered by the compute and storage EGI services above.

3.3.5. Cross-node integration and federation aspects

EGI Pilot Node has provided e-infrastructure services to thematic and national nodes in need of computational, storage and virtual research environments.

It has also provided EGI Check-in to other Pilot Nodes that wanted to exploit existing integrations and did not have the resources to deploy a dedicated AAI infrastructure.

Pilot Nodes including MetroFood, Lifewatch, ENES, INSTRUCT and NFDI have presented cross-node user stories involving EGI Pilot Node exchange services.

Building these connections between Pilots based on the needs and requirements of scientific user stories is a bottom-up approach for establishing the pilot federation. It is still to be explored whether these connections are best established on an ad hoc basis as research needs emerge, or if a more structural approach that enforces some links based on regular or common patterns of interaction is necessary.

3.3.6. Technical implementation status, challenges and solutions

By M18, EGI Pilot node has exposed all its exchange services to the EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox. These are available to either support researchers directly or other Pilot Nodes to deliver their user stories.

The distributed nature of the EGI Federation has made the integration with the Core services a straightforward step due to the extensive experience of the EGI Foundation in the establishment of Federated environments. Operating these services in the context of the newly established EOSC Federation architecture is a natural step yet challenging

to achieve in coordination with all contributing Pilots. A strong collaboration with the Service teams who are in charge of developing the core and innovation services according to Pilot needs has been key to support the technical implementations.

During the next phase, EGI Pilot Node will explore the Federation of Services supported by a dedicated instance of the Services Catalogue to automate service discoverability in other Pilot Nodes compatible with the solution.

3.4. e-INFRA CZ

3.4.1. Node Profile and integration goals

e-INFRA CZ, sometimes referred to as *MetaCentrum*, is a Czech national computing infrastructure for academic use, providing high-throughput compute services through a number of low-level interfaces (batch computing, IaaS cloud, container orchestration platform) as well as higher-level portals (Jupyter Notebooks, Galaxy). Existing resources can be assigned and re-assigned to different methods of use based on community demand.

The node brings together major resource operators in Czech academia, and also resource contributions from individual academic establishments willing to pool their processing capacity. At the beginning of 2025 the node comprised over 47 thousand CPUs, 480 GP-GPUs, and 3.5 thousand active users. Over the previous year, users clocked over 37 thousand CPU years across the node infrastructure, with all access options (batch, cloud, container, ...) combined.

The existing user community around the node is a generic one for academia and research, strictly non-commercial. It does not have a specific focus on any field of science, although the areas of bioinformatics, particle physics and Earth observation are mildly preferred.

Regarding the federation efforts within EOSC Beyond, the environment is already built on tools and technologies intended for the project, which opens up the option to set higher goals, specifically to aim at achieving cross-node functionality. As there are numerous user interfaces within the node, for the purpose of EOSC Beyond a narrower focus is put more specifically on the managed interactive notebooks platform (Jupyter Notebooks), and many of the goals and achievements of e-INFRA CZ pilot integration are considered in the context of the notebooks service.

The managed **notebooks platform** builds specifically on the infrastructure cloud interface. It is a repeatable deployment of a Jupyter Hub multi-user server offering different integrations with the existing services within the ecosystem, especially those for storage. Accessing data stored elsewhere within the nodes federation is, after all, a focus of the cross-node integration effort in this project. It will be considered successfully achieved if the user story can be successfully supported, that is, if users from other nodes can cooperate on resources (datasets, notebooks) authored or otherwise offered by native users of e-INFRA CZ.

3.4.2. Scientific user stories

e-Infra Cz-SUS-1: Cross-Border Collaboration

As a user with an account in Czech AAI, I have an account in e-INFRA CZ Node. I want to invite colleagues from other countries, give them access to my project, etc.

Relevant services: AAI

e-Infra Cz-SUS-2: Repeatable data science – As a user I have found useful data in some thematic data repositories. I need to get access to this data, I need to download them to my local storage in my Node, do analysis in Notebook service there and later publish this Notebook to Notebook service provided by EOSC EU Node and give access to my colleagues.

Relevant services: AAI, PID Service, Data Transfer, Notebooks, Storage

3.4.3. Use and feedback of core services

AAI
<p>Status: Done</p> <p>The primary service used in the integration is AAI. As explained above, the underlying technologies and solutions relevant to EOSC Beyond are already used in e-INFRA CZ, therefore the integration process was more or less routine, and it can now be considered done. So far the IaaS Cloud (OpenStack) and the Interactive Notebooks Service (JupyterHub) are integrated with AAI.</p>
Other core services
<p>Other core services used are the Service Catalogue and the Helpdesk. No special technical integration has been performed in that respect: the services are used directly in core, although M2M integration with the Helpdesk is sought after and is a long-time ambition.</p>

Table 7: e-Infra CZ use of core services

3.4.4. e-Infra CZ Pilot Node exchange services

Principal exchange services used in this context are the IaaS cloud, storage and repository services, all instances available locally at CESNET, and are even onboarded (or expected to be onboarded) in the service catalogue as part of the pilot node. Given that, the adoption of those underlying services is simple and does not present particular obstacles or challenges. Future focus will be put on streamlining the use of the scientific repository from within the Notebooks environment – for the time being only proof-of-concept tests have been performed.

3.4.5. Cross-node integration and federation aspects

From the cross-node use aspect the Interactive Notebooks environment has the advantage of being well configurable and adjustable, with many options for user-space automation, handling of secrets and choice of protocols and authentication methods in accessing data and services.

Users in the Notebooks environment can have their OIDC tokens available for direct use, injected automatically on login or by a purpose-built JupyterLab extension. This allows them to perform token exchange with fine-grained control, relying on scripts, environment extensions, or program snippets included directly in their notebooks. Many of these features are also included in the FedCloud horizontal adapter, developed within the suite of EOSC Beyond Integration Suite's Horizontal Adapters.

Having an environment programmable to such an extent, as the Interactive Notebooks service, makes it possible to pioneer cross-site use in areas where it cannot be supported by existing user-facing solutions.

Simple usage scenarios such as injecting extra-realm tokens, or using services such as KeyCloak to obtain specific API tokens for services in a manner of token exchange have already been tested.

3.4.6. Technical implementation status, challenges and solutions

By month 18, the deployment of the notebooks service is self-contained. That is, it is installed in a dedicated chunk (OpenStack project) of cloud infrastructure provided by the resource provider (CESNET). All the necessary components, including the default (or fall-back) user home storage are deployed in the same environment. This simplifies catering to users who come from other nodes within the federation. In the case of the e-INFRA CZ Notebooks this role is performed by a dedicated NFS server, wherefrom user home directories are mounted directly into their jupyter server environments on start-up. Unless the user is identified as a "national" user with home storage space already provisioned elsewhere in the node: in that case their existing home is mounted instead.

In the next reporting period, we will automate integration with other components in the ecosystem to the extent it's practical. For instance, based on the user's group membership or entitlements, alternative locations for storing their home directories (OwnCloud, institutional NFS, ...) can be used, with the default NFS storage as a fall-back. This capability is being considered mainly for native e-INFRA CZ users, but when in place, other communities might benefit as well. As explained in the previous section, even cross-realm connectivity can be supported to some extent (*scope and hardening to be progressed next period*).

An important security challenge was identified in the co-existence of two key features of the Interactive Notebooks Service. On one hand there's the convenient way the user's OIDC token is injected into their environment on log-in to facilitate integration with a plethora of services available in the node or even across nodes. On the other hand

there's the Real Time Collaboration feature, which allows the user to invite others to share in their running environment, potentially giving them access -- to some extent surreptitious -- to their authentication secrets, i.e., the tokens that have been made available for their use automatically.

By month 18, the challenge outlined above has been addressed in two ways. Firstly, the default behaviour of injecting the token has been made optional, and it is controllable in the Jupyter Hub management screen before the user starts their environment. Secondly an enhanced JupyterLab extension has been provided to give the user ability to obtain their token from their browser session's auth state, and also to check and warn if they are initiating an environment sharing session with live (valid) tokens available.

3.5. ENES

3.5.1. Node Profile and integration goals

The ENES Pilot Node designed in the framework of the EOSC Beyond project aims to deliver a scalable, interoperable, verifiable, and provenance-aware data science environment, addressing the key challenges and needs encountered by scientists in their daily research activities, mainly in the climate science domain.

More specifically, ENES acts as a thematic node combining the newly developed EOSC Core services with existing ENES services. This comprises infrastructure components for service deployment and orchestration, data such as input datasets and research products, cloud resources including storage and computation, and software tools that assist researchers and institutional departments in practical scientific scenarios.

The ENES infrastructure enables scientific user to run Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning applications, perform big data processing and interactive analytics, and visualize climate data without needing to download datasets, install software, or set up an environment. It also provides a provenance management service, complemented by a provenance explorer that enables the publication, navigation, tracking, and interactive exploration of the lineage of data processing workflow in both textual and graphical formats, fully compliant with **W3C PROV standards**.

The EOSC-related goal is to showcase the smooth integration of EOSC Core services within a pilot infrastructure, while identifying areas for improvement. It also facilitates broader access to ENES Exchange services by registering them in service catalogues and making them available through the EOSC Discovery Hub, thus supporting interoperability and federated access across multiple Nodes.

More specifically, the ENES Pilot Node aims to advance open science in climate research by addressing real-world scientific needs through user-driven stories and by strengthening collaboration across research infrastructures. This includes integrating a wide range of EOSC Core Services to support a federated ecosystem. In addition, the Node focuses on incorporating key services and tools for data access and cataloguing,

making thematic data collections easier to discover and use across the broader EOSC federation.

3.5.2. Scientific user stories

The typical workflow of a climate researcher involves several steps, including the search and discovery of relevant datasets, their processing and analysis to extract meaningful information, the visualization of results to ensure clarity and accessibility, and the interpretation of findings to support scientific knowledge and decision-making processes, with data provenance practices applied throughout the workflow to guarantee transparency, traceability, and reliability.

The ENES Pilot Node encompasses a set of dedicated services aiming to fully support the researchers' workflow. More specifically, scientists can easily search for their desired datasets against the ENES data catalogue and proceed to perform their experiments or data analysis within the ENESLab environment, following appropriate access authorization. Upon successful experiments, the resulting provenance document, structured according to the W3C PROV standard, is uploaded to the provenance service, which enables graphical visualization and exploration of the data lineage information.

Following the two user stories implemented in the context of the EOSC Beyond project:

ENES-SUS-1: Perform interactive analysis and visualization on scientific data

As a scientist, I want to get access to computing resources so that I can run interactive analysis, AI/ML-based applications, and visualization on scientific data.

Researcher Perspective:

- The scientist browses the public ENES data catalogue to search for the desired data collections, which are published to the EOSC Discovery Hub.
- Similarly, the scientist discovers the ENESLab (ENES data science environment) service from the EOSC Discovery Hub and accesses it (through the EOSC AAI) requesting the required compute and storage resources.
- The scientist gets access to a ready-to-use Jupyter environment including data, co-located compute resources, and a fully configured data science software stack.
- The scientist runs data analytics and visualization on the selected datasets.

Related Nodes: ENES, EGI, CESNET, EOSC Sandbox

EOSC Services: AAI, Service Catalogue, EOSC Discovery Hub, Service Monitoring, Helpdesk, Deployment Service.

ENES-SUS-2: Manage provenance information associated with scientific workflows

As a scientist, I want to run my analytics workflow (achieved in ENES-SUS-1) and publish and/or manage provenance information at different levels of granularity.

Researcher Perspective:

- The scientist gets a provenance document, which is generated at runtime on ENESLab during the workflow execution.
- The scientist uploads the provenance document to the provenance service, accessing it through the EOSC AAI via the EGI token portal.
- After successfully uploading, the scientist can retrieve and visualize the provenance graph in an image format from the ENESLab.
- Furthermore, the scientist can explore the provenance graph interactively through the Provenance Explorer software tool.

Related Nodes: ENES, EGI, EOSC Sandbox

EOSC Services: AAI, Service Catalogue, EOSC Discovery Hub, Service Monitoring, Helpdesk.

Figure 5: ENES Use Cases flow

3.5.3. Use and feedback of core services

AAI

Status of Integration: Done

Feedback: The technical details provided by the service owner were clear and forthright towards the integration of the EOSC AAI with the ENES services. It facilitates our own ENES infrastructure proxy, which connects and controls access to ENES services from other nodes, manages identity enrolment and user authentication, and enables federated capabilities. Through the addition of other pilot node entitlements supplied by the service owner, the ENES infrastructure proxy will be consolidated for cross-node validation.

Lessons Learned: It's a beta version of the EOSC AAI supported via EGI Check-in Demo to access the ENES services. After completion of the project in the production stage, we believe a complete setup should be installed for the ENES infrastructure proxy supported by the service owner.

Helpdesk

<p>Status of Integration: Done <i>Feedback:</i> The integration was fairly simple because of the smooth settings created and shared by the service owner.</p>
Monitoring
<p>Status of Integration: Done <i>Feedback:</i> Since the majority of the work was done by the service owner, integration was straightforward. ENES just needed to provide the service URLs of the dedicated endpoints to the service owner for monitoring. <i>Additional Requirements:</i> Alerting when an endpoint becomes unavailable.</p>
Service Catalogue
<p>Status of Integration: Done <i>Feedback:</i> When a new ENES service is deployed and available to the end users, a new entry is added to the service catalogue. The process is quite simple; the validation messages could be improved to make errors self-explanatory.</p>
EOSC Discovery Hub
<p>Status of Integration: Done <i>Feedback:</i> Considering that EOSC Discovery Hub and Service Catalog are automatically kept synchronized and permission authority is verified in the background, the process can be considered efficient.</p>
Deployment Service
<p>Status of Integration: Done <i>Feedback:</i> specifying a cloud application's topology through a TOSCA template is not always immediate; however, the regular support provided by the service owner made both the service template definition and the deployment phase quite smooth. TOSCA templates and artifacts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://github.com/grycap/tosca/blob/new_stac/templates/enes.yaml • https://github.com/grycap/tosca/blob/new_stac/artifacts/enes/enes.yml • https://github.com/grycap/tosca/blob/new_stac/artifacts/stac_compose.yml • https://github.com/grycap/tosca/blob/new_stac/templates/yProv.yml

Table 8: ENES use of core services

3.5.4. ENES Pilot Node exchange services

ENESLab represents a data science environment, providing a scalable, cloud-enabled platform designed to support the growing need for data-intensive scientific workflows in the climate research community and beyond.

Built on top of Jupyter technologies, ENESLab offers an interactive computing environment that simplifies the analysis and visualization of large-scale climate datasets. It integrates various open-source tools optimized for parallel processing, making it well-suited for advanced scientific workflows. Users can securely access ENESLab through the following endpoint at <https://ds.eneslab.pilot.eosc-beyond.eu/jupyter/hub/login>, with login managed via the EOSC AAI system to ensure trusted and federated authentication across other pilot nodes. ENESLab also supports the generation of provenance documents in JSON format compliant with the W3C Prov standard, thus enabling the upload to the provenance service for future use and exploration.

Provenance Service - yProv

One of the main components of the ENES provenance-enabled data science environment is the provenance service (yProv), which is designed to collect and manage provenance information in complex, data-driven scientific experiments in various domains, thus ensuring the reproducibility and trustworthiness of scientific results.

More specifically, yProv is a web service accessible via the dedicated web endpoint at <http://yprov.disi.unitn.it:3000>, which supports secure, federated access through the EOSC AAI, using the EGI token introspection mechanism. Its smooth operation throughout the EOSC ecosystem allows for interoperability with scientific operations that adhere to W3C PROV standards.

yProv acts as a client to a graph database backend that handles all required operations via RESTful API calls, i.e., the creation, reading, updating, and deletion of provenance records (CRUD). There are several approaches for users to investigate provenance metadata, which offer a deeper comprehension of the history and provenance of scientific data.

The yProv software ecosystem also provides a software tool, called Provenance Explorer, for accessing, exploring and navigating the provenance documents. In order to guarantee flexibility and wide applicability in data science processes, the provenance explorer, which can be accessed via <https://explorer.yprov.disi.unitn.it/>, enables users to upload provenance documents in JSON format using three distinct methods: local storage file upload, URL reference, and API call. Following a successful upload, the provenance explorer displays the provenance graph both graphically and textually, emphasizing the number of nodes, entities, activities, and agents involved as a part of the uploaded provenance document.

Thematic Data Catalogue

Data search and discovery are essential steps for unlocking the full value of research data. Without efficient ways to locate, access, and understand datasets, even the most valuable data can remain underutilized. In the context of the EOSC Beyond project, a small set of climate collections have been organized and exposed through a thematic data catalogue implemented following the SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog (STAC) specification, thus enabling standardized metadata, powerful search capabilities, and seamless integration across platforms. To fully leverage the STAC specification, the STAC Browser and STAC API have been deployed to offer intuitive tools and programmatic access for exploring, querying, and integrating geospatial datasets. Here are the corresponding endpoints:

STAC Browser: <https://catalogue.eneslab.pilot.eosc-beyond.eu/>

STAC API: <https://catalogue.eneslab.pilot.eosc-beyond.eu/api/>

Table 9: ENES Exchange services

3.5.5. Cross-node integration and federation aspects

The compute and storage resources used to deploy the ENES Exchange Services are provided by the CESNET provider on the **e-INFRA OpenStack cloud** site located in Brno. More specifically, the ENESLab consists of a Kubernetes cluster deployed and configured using the EOSC Deployment Service and more specifically the Infrastructure Manager (IM) tool developed by UPV; the ENES data collections are stored in ZARR format on an object storage system to guarantee fast and efficient data access and analysis.

The ENES Community AAI (based on the EGI Check-in) has been integrated with the other EOSC Beyond pilot nodes' Community AAIs. As a result, the ENES exchange services can be also accessed by researchers from other pilot nodes, enabling them to authenticate with their institutional or social media accounts. In this way, any researcher can access the ENESLab and get compute resources for running interactive analysis and visualization. Similarly, as the provenance service integrates the EOSC AAI as well, scientists from different research groups or communities can easily share and access provenance documents stored in a standardized way, thus promoting interoperability and collaboration.

Moreover, the ENES thematic data catalogue has been onboarded to the Sandbox Service Catalogue, thus making it available into the EOSC Discovery Hub. Additionally, work is ongoing to enable OAI-PMH harvesting of ENES dataset metadata into the EOSC Knowledge Graph. This will allow researchers to discover and retrieve the required datasets directly from the EOSC Discovery Hub

3.5.6. Technical implementation status, challenges and solutions

To achieve federated capabilities across multiple pilot nodes and enable the scientific user stories (ENES-SUS-1 and ENES-SUS-2) described above, ENES completed several key integration activities during the first phase of the project (M1-M18). More

specifically, the ENES exchange services, such as ENESLab and the Provenance Service, have been successfully integrated with the following EOSC Core services: AAI, Service Catalogue, Helpdesk, Service Monitoring and Deployment Service. In addition, ENES is fully discoverable in the EOSC Discovery Hub, it has already been registered as an EOSC provider in the Sandbox Service Catalogue, it disclosed its Jupyter-based data science environment and provenance service (including the explorer tool), and it made its thematic data catalogue available as a data source. The EOSC AAI has been integrated with ENESLab and the provenance service, exploiting the ENES Infrastructure Proxy which is in charge of connecting and managing access to the node services. Additionally, the EOSC monitoring service is keeping an eye on both services to get statistics about availability and reliability, while a dedicated support system based on the EOSC Helpdesk allows users to get assistance about both ENES services. Only minor problems have been encountered during the integration phase, mostly related to bugs, missing features and incomplete documentation. Feedback was promptly provided to ensure these issues are addressed over time.

Future activities will still focus on the reinforcement of the ENES user stories in order to implement a complete user journey and strengthen the integration with the EOSC core services as well as the link with the other pilot nodes. More specifically, some activities planned for the second part of the project include:

- the integration with the Research Product Catalogue to facilitate the harvesting of ENES datasets' metadata by the EOSC Knowledge Graph and the publication within the EOSC Discovery Hub;
- the integration of PID service capabilities within the ENES user stories;
- the enhancement of the helpdesk core capability;
- the consolidation of the monitoring service across various dimensions or parameters;
- testing and validation of the ENES node capabilities.

3.6. INSTRUCT-ERIC

3.6.1. Node Profile and integration goals

The Instruct-ERIC Node aims to serve the Instruct-ERIC and Structural Biology community, specifically with the goals of helping the community manage the data they produce and make it FAIR.

Instruct provides access to structural biology services and technologies to researchers via its access management platform ARIA. As a distributed research infrastructure, Instruct has facilities across Europe, and as such an Instruct access workflow may require input from multiple facilities, representing an "Integrated Structural biology" pipeline.

The Instruct-ERIC Node has two primary goals – the first to pilot storage brokering using storage provided by other Pilot Nodes, brokered by ARIA and provisioned by Instruct's facility side Laboratory Information Management System (LIMS) orchestration tool

FandanGO, to store raw experimental data and link it to a researcher's visit information within ARIA. The second is to then have this data published, after an embargo period, to the Sandbox catalogue within EOSC Beyond.

3.6.2. Scientific user stories

Instruct-SUS-1: Researcher upload data for Cloud storage

A researcher visits a small Instruct facility to perform some structural biology research. During the experiment, raw data is generated which the researcher will want to perform subsequent processing on, and the facility would like to publish and make available to follow-on research after an embargo period.

While it is routine within the community to publish processed results to the various repositories (e.g PDB), the retention and publishing of raw data is less common, which is unfortunate as this data can be reexamined and reprocessed to produce new results. With the advent of AI, even so-called "negative results" can be invaluable in the construction of models. Unfortunately, smaller facilities rarely have sufficient storage to hold these data long term, and so we want to connect those facilities and their researchers to other partners in the Instruct node network that are able to help.

Using Instruct FandanGO's suite of tools, they are able to ask the ARIA platform, based on the researcher details (home country, funding body, etc, all found in the research proposal "visit" record in ARIA) which storage options are available within the network. Once selected, storage is provisioned, and the upload of the raw data is handled by FandanGO and the location and details of how to access the data are stored against the visit record within ARIA.

Additionally to these data being linked to the scientific proposal within ARIA, after an embargo period, the raw data held on the cloud storage will be made available in the EOSC catalogue via a public repository such as OpenAIRE, providing FAIR access to the data. The data can then be accessed via the ARIA data catalogue and downloaded from the storage provider.

This will be piloted using data produced by the CNB-CSIC Pilot Node, from a researcher visiting the facility in Madrid. Cloud storage will be provided, in this pilot, by using an instance of OneData hosted by the [EOSC.pl](https://www.eosc.eu) (via EGI Data Hub), with an ambition to extend this capability with other providers in the future.

Figure 6: Instruct-SUS-1 flow diagram

Figure 6 Instruct-SUS-1 flow diagram displays an outline of the main user story of this use case. A user applies to access Instruct services from the Discovery Hub, creating a tracked visit within Instruct ARIA. The facility manager, e.g. at another Pilot Node like CNB-CSIC, tracks the visit, and requests data storage provision from the EGI Pilot Node via the EOSC.pl OneData provider, using the Instruct FandanGO toolkit. Once provisioned, the raw data from the research visit can be uploaded and stored in the node's storage service, and also (after some embargo period) published and made discoverable on a public repository like OpenAIRE, which can then be consumed by the Discovery Hub and accessed and downloaded from OneData via ARIA's data catalogue.

3.6.3. Use and feedback of core services

AAI
<p>Integration status: To be done</p> <p>Feedback: Currently unable to configure ARIA IDSS's KeyCloak-based AAI system (version 11.3) to enable scripts for scope mapping as an identity provider (IDP) in EGI Check-In. Also unable to have ARIA's historical EGI Check-In connection re-established. No further solutions are currently available.</p>
Helpdesk
<p>Integration status: Done</p> <p>Feedback: Integration was straightforward. Sustainability and privacy remain primary concerns.</p>
PID
<p>Integration status: Done</p> <p>Feedback: This is an extra which is done via OneData as they provide us a handler service to push records to the Cloud (OpenAire) and is still in progress</p>

Service Catalogue
<p>Integration status: In progress</p> <p>Feedback: Publishing of raw/processed data to the EOSC catalogue is still in progress</p>
EOSC Discovery Hub
<p>Integration status: Done</p> <p>Feedback: Thanks to the group workshop, instrument services were added to the Sandbox by the CESSDA node, which links to the corresponding items in ARIA's machine booking system.</p>

Table 10: INSTRUCT-ERIC use of core services

3.6.4. Instruct-ERIC Pilot Node exchange services

Instruct-ERIC (ARIA/Fandango)

A researcher can discover services on the EOSC User Space and request access via ARIA. A facility manager can broker a storage option from a network of options presented in FandanGO as provided by ARIA, then provision storage from Fandango and upload their raw data.

3.6.5. Cross-node integration and federation aspects

CESSDA

Instruct-ERIC's ARIA platform being federated in the Sandbox, in this instance, instruments, for all Pilot Nodes to access. Researchers can find instruments for their research here and book a slot to use the chosen instrument in ARIA as part of their research. This is of benefit to researchers, as they can find the instruments of their choice via any Node in the network, and for Instruct-ERIC to make our services available to a wider audience.

Cyfronet Storage (OneData/EGI datahub)

Using Instruct-ERIC's FandanGo toolset at facilities, the facility manager and/or researcher can choose from a selection of storage options available on the Instruct network, provided by ARIA. Of these, OneData is provided as an option to be selected. Storage space is then provisioned to the user and made available for data upload. After uploading metadata and raw data, we will retrieve a location of the storage and then feed it back to ARIA. A link of the storage will be provided for researchers to access at any time, and to make available to the public when reaching its embargo period.

CNB-CSIC

CNB-CSIC - FandanGO is developed in collaboration with CNB-CSIC and they are the facility that is piloting the use of FandanGO's storage brokering capabilities for their research visits.

Future developments that could be made possible by this use case may involve integrating CNB-CSIC's facility LIMS and data validation systems – including their cryo-EM Validation Report Service (VRS) and Scipion workflows – with Instruct FandanGO to streamline their workflows and make publishing both raw and processed data more streamlined and FAIR for their visiting researchers.

3.6.6. Technical implementation status, challenges and solutions

The technical implementation of the Instruct ERIC pilot within EOSC Beyond has focused on storage brokering. No issues or blockers were encountered when implementing this functionality with the PL node/EGI providing storage via OneData. We can prove the concept of a facility manager or researcher (user) using Instruct-ERIC's FandanGo toolset to upload data and retrieve data from OneData. An additional outcome is that the data stored in the OneData can then be made available to the public after an embargo period.

Helpdesk integration was straightforward, however we have concerns of sustainability and security/privacy, specifically in terms of availability after the project has ended.

Furthermore, AAI integration is blocked due to incompatibility issues regarding the latest version of EGI Check-in and ARIA IDSS. This is despite the fact that there was a pre-existing connection between the two systems, but has since been disabled. It would be out of the scope of this project to make the changes necessary to re-establish compatibility between these two systems.

Phase 1 (M1-M18) of the Instruct Pilot will succeed when Instruct services are made available on the Discovery Hub and Instruct FandanGO can request and be provisioned storage from ARIA's storage network, connect with **EOSC.pl** OneData storage provider, and upload data. Phase 2 (M19-M36) will see completion of the full story whereby uploaded data is then published to a public repository such as OpenAIRE (after an embargo period) and then synced to the Discovery Hub, where a user can then request access and download the data.

3.7. LifeWatch ERIC

3.7.1. Node Profile and integration goals

LifeWatch ERIC is a European Research Infrastructure providing e-Science research facilities to scientists investigating biodiversity and ecosystem functions and services in order to support society in addressing key planetary challenges. The main focus of

LifeWatch ERIC is to enable data-driven, reproducible, and collaborative research in the fields of biodiversity, ecology, and environmental science. Its main stakeholders are researchers, students and policy makers. One of the key platforms is the **LifeWatch ERIC Metadata Catalogue**, which is based on **GeoNetwork** and is dedicated to the creation, management and publication of metadata about resources related to biodiversity and ecosystem domain. It hosts metadata of six kinds of resources: datasets, services, Virtual Research Environments (VREs), workflows, training resources and research sites.

Within the context of EOSC Beyond project LifeWatch ERIC exposes itself as a provider and contributes with the federation of the LifeWatch ERIC Metadata Catalogue with the EOSC Sandbox Service Catalogue. This integration supports seamless discovery, access and reuse of services developed within LifeWatch ERIC through the EOSC Discovery Hub.

As a use case, the pilot features a service focused on the analysis of alien species distribution across aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems. This service allows researchers to integrate, clean, and analyse biodiversity data, ensuring consistency in taxonomic identification and alien species classification. Through its integration into EOSC, the service becomes discoverable via the federated catalogue in the EOSC Discovery Hub, where researchers can directly access the EGI Cloud environment to run the service. The required datasets are also available through the EOSC Discovery Hub, and EOSC AAI supports secure authentication. The Helpdesk is available for additional support or troubleshooting if required.

The main EOSC-related goals of the LifeWatch ERIC pilot are to achieve full interoperability and integration with EOSC Core services, enabling broader accessibility and reuse of LifeWatch services through the EOSC ecosystem. This includes the federation of the LifeWatch Metadata Catalogue with the EOSC Sandbox Service Catalogue, ensuring that services are discoverable and aligned with EOSC metadata standards. In addition, the pilot aims to leverage the Deployment Service and the Order Management System to provide automated, user-friendly execution of LifeWatch services directly through the EOSC Discovery Hub. Another key goal is the integration of EOSC AAI, allowing researchers to authenticate using federated credentials, and the connection with the EOSC Helpdesk, enabling streamlined user support.

Success for the LifeWatch ERIC pilot in EOSC Beyond is defined by the seamless integration of its Metadata Catalogue into the EOSC ecosystem, enabling real-world scientific use cases. This includes the successful harvesting of LifeWatch metadata resources into the Sandbox Service Catalogue, making them discoverable to researchers across Europe. It also means that a researcher can easily find a relevant service, such as the alien species analysis use case, access its metadata and initiate the creation of a service instance. Ultimately, the pilot demonstrates that LifeWatch ERIC services can be effectively exposed, accessed, and used within the EOSC framework, providing a blueprint for future integrations of domain-specific research infrastructures.

3.7.2. Scientific user stories

LifeWatch ERIC-SUS-1: Analysis of alien species incidence across ecosystems

One of the major environmental challenges of recent decades is the introduction and spread of alien species in ecosystems where they are not native. This phenomenon has raised significant concerns within the scientific community and beyond, due to its potential impacts on biodiversity, ecosystem functioning, and socio-economic systems. In response, research efforts have increasingly focused on understanding and mitigating the effects of biological invasions. In this context, the user story developed for the EOSC Beyond pilot highlights a service designed to support such efforts.

More specifically, LifeWatch ERIC's user story demonstrates how researchers can discover and access a specialised service that facilitates the integration, cleaning and analysis of biodiversity datasets containing records of both native and alien species. The analysis begins with the integration of five georeferenced datasets spanning multiple ecosystems (marine, transitional, freshwater and terrestrial). Once integrated, the service performs a data cleaning process, including a taxonomic validation and a check of each species' alien status. The final steps involve the calculation and visualisation of species abundance, along with an assessment of the incidence of alien species across different habitats and ecosystem types.

To access the service, the researcher begins by visiting the EOSC Discovery Hub, where the LifeWatch ERIC Metadata Catalogue has been exposed into the EOSC Service Catalogue. By entering relevant keywords (e.g. "alien species"), the researcher can discover the related service. The metadata record provides a detailed description of the service, its functionality, and guidance on how to initiate its use.

Once the researcher identifies the service of interest, they press to access it and are redirected to the service webpage, which in this case is the LifeWatch ERIC Metadata Catalogue. From there, the user can launch the service, and its execution is handled through the Deployment Service, which automates the provisioning of the required computational environment. In the current setup this is triggered from the command line, while in the future it will be managed through the Order Management System, enabling users to launch the service directly from the EOSC Discovery Hub interface. The underlying cloud resources, such as EGI Cloud Compute, provide the virtual environment where the code runs, while the required datasets are accessible through the EOSC Discovery Hub. The Helpdesk is available as an optional support channel, should the researcher have additional questions or require assistance. This step is facilitated through EOSC AAI, allowing the researcher to authenticate using their credentials.

Figure 7: LifeWatch ERIC-SUS-1 flow diagram

3.7.3. Use and feedback of core services

AAI
<p>Status of integration: Done</p> <p>EOSC AAI has been successfully implemented within the LifeWatch ERIC environment, allowing researchers to authenticate using their credentials.</p>
Helpdesk
<p>Status of integration: In progress</p> <p>A feasibility study has been conducted, and the Helpdesk workflow has been successfully tested. The setup allows researchers to create a support ticket linked to a specific service, which is then routed to the LifeWatch ERIC technical team.</p> <p>Additional requirements: the work has exploited results coming from the EOSC Future project.</p>
Service Catalogue
<p>Status of integration: In progress</p> <p>LifeWatch ERIC has been successfully registered as a provider in the Sandbox Service Catalogue. The LifeWatch ERIC Metadata Catalogue has also been federated as a data source. The service developed for the user story is fully published in the Sandbox and accessible through the EOSC Discovery Hub.</p> <p>Feedback: A more clear and guided process to achieve this integration by all the involved parties would have been needed to accelerate the output achievement.</p>

Additional requirements: We still need to enable the datasets and services to be harvestable through OAI-PMH into the EOSC Knowledge Graph through OpenAIRE. To achieve this, being the dataset metadata schema of the LifeWatch ERIC Metadata Catalogue based on EML, an XSL Transformation is needed to follow the OpenAIRE guidelines for Literature Repositories.

Deployment service

Status of integration: Done

The Deployment Service has been adopted as a core service to automate the provisioning of computational environments for LifeWatch ERIC services. At the moment, execution is triggered from the command line, but the setup is functional and tested in the Sandbox.

Additional requirements: Future work will include tighter integration with the EOSC Discovery Hub so that services can be launched directly via user interaction with the LifeWatch ERIC Metadata Catalogue.

Order Management System

Status of integration: In progress

The Order Management System will be integrated as a core service in the next phase, enabling parameterised requests and direct execution of services from the EOSC Discovery Hub interface. This will complete the workflow from service discovery to automated deployment and execution.

Additional requirements: Implementation of the URL parameter handling between the LifeWatch Metadata Catalogue, Discovery Hub, and Order Management System will be needed to support user-driven launches.

Table 11: LifeWatch ERIC use of core services

3.7.4. LifeWatch ERIC Pilot Node exchange services

The **LifeWatch ERIC Metadata Catalogue** provides a platform for the creation, management, and publication of metadata for biodiversity-related resources, including datasets, and services. Through its integration with the EOSC Sandbox Catalogue, it enables the federation and discovery of LifeWatch services and datasets in the EOSC Discovery Hub, making them accessible to a broader research community. This catalogue is essential for supporting the user story, as it publishes the metadata record of the alien species analysis service and the associated datasets required for running the analysis in the EGI Cloud environment.

Technical details and next steps: Work is ongoing to allow the OpenAIRE Knowledge Graph to be developed by harvesting metadata records coming from the LifeWatch ERIC Metadata Catalogue. A key step in this process is the development of an XSL Transformation to map the metadata standards used by LifeWatch ERIC (EML 2.2.0 and ISO 19139) to the DataCite standard adopted by OpenAIRE, together with the configuration of the OAI-PMH protocol, allowing LifeWatch datasets to be ingested into the EOSC Knowledge Graph. The XSLT will also be made available through the EOSC

Integration Suite to support other pilots facing similar metadata harmonisation challenges.

3.7.5. Cross-node integration and federation aspects

Within the EOSC Beyond, LifeWatch ERIC and EGI have been collaborating closely to create an integrated workflow. LifeWatch ERIC contributed its Metadata Catalogue, which provides detailed metadata records for biodiversity services and datasets, including those required for the above-mentioned user story. EGI, on the other hand, offers its Cloud infrastructure, which will host and execute the R-based workflow. The EGI Cloud provides the virtualized computational environment required to run the R-based analysis workflow for the alien species incidence service. Researchers will directly access this environment through the EOSC Discovery Hub, where the service and the required datasets will be available. The analysis code will be executed within the EGI Cloud infrastructure without the need for technical intervention from LifeWatch ERIC.

The connection between these layers is enabled through the Deployment Service, which automates the provisioning of the required computational environment. Currently this process is triggered manually, while in the future the Order Management System (OMS) will enable users to launch services directly from the EOSC Discovery Hub interface. Once the datasets are fully harvested into the EOSC Knowledge Graph, researchers will be able to discover both the datasets and the service in the EOSC Discovery Hub and directly run the workflow within the EGI Cloud environment.

Several federation mechanisms have been tested. LifeWatch ERIC successfully integrated the AAI, ensuring that researchers can authenticate with their credentials to access both LifeWatch services and the EGI Cloud environment. Additionally, the LifeWatch Metadata Catalogue was exposed in the Sandbox Service Catalogue, making the alien species analysis service discoverable through the EOSC Discovery Hub. Work is ongoing to enable OAI-PMH harvesting of dataset metadata into the EOSC Knowledge Graph, which will complete the connection between data, services, and computational workflows. The planned data flow involves researchers retrieving the required datasets directly from the Discovery Hub and processing them in the EGI Cloud without additional technical intervention.

This cross-node integration brings significant benefits to LifeWatch's user story and its broader community of stakeholders. By combining LifeWatch's expertise in biodiversity and ecosystem research with EGI's robust computational infrastructure, it enables the scientific community to easily discover, access, and execute services within a single, integrated EOSC ecosystem, ensuring a smooth and efficient research experience.

3.7.6. Technical implementation status, challenges and solutions

From M1 to M18, the technical implementation of the LifeWatch ERIC pilot within EOSC Beyond has focused on achieving federation with the EOSC Sandbox Service Catalogue, enabling AAI integration, and preparing the EGI Cloud environment to run the alien species analysis workflow. So far, LifeWatch ERIC has successfully registered as an

EOSC provider, exposed its Metadata Catalogue as a data source, and published the alien species analysis service so it is fully discoverable via the EOSC Discovery Hub. EOSC AAI has been integrated into the LifeWatch ERIC environment. Additionally, the Helpdesk integration is almost completed and ready for final adjustments. The Deployment Service has been adopted as a core service to automate the provisioning of computational environments, with initial tests already conducted. Integration of the Order Management System is planned as the next step, which will allow users to launch services directly from the Discovery Hub interface.

From M18 onwards, the focus will shift to completing the remaining technical tasks, in particular the integration of the Order Management System and the finalisation of dataset harvesting from OpenAIRE via OAI-PMH. Significant progress has already been made on developing an XSL transformation that converts the LifeWatch ERIC dataset metadata schema into the OpenAIRE-compliant format. This transformation will also be made available through the EOSC Adapter Suite, so that other pilots facing similar metadata alignment challenges can benefit from this work. Once the harvesting process is complete, the next step will be to perform a full end-to-end test of the service execution, covering the workflow from service discovery in the Discovery Hub, through request handling by the Order Management System, to automated deployment by the Deployment Service on the EGI Cloud environment. So far, no major issues have arisen, and regular meetings with the technical teams from OpenAIRE and EGI are ensuring steady progress on the user story.

3.8. METROFOOD-RI

3.8.1. Node Profile and integration goals

The METROFOOD-RI Pilot Node is a specialized implementation within the EOSC Beyond network of Pilot Nodes focused on advancing food quality, food safety, and sustainability through metrology-based research and services. Representing a Research Infrastructure, METROFOOD-RI supports a broad scientific community working in food chemistry, biological sciences, environmental science and related disciplines. Its infrastructure combines physical and electronic components, including analytical laboratories, reference material collections, and data catalogues.

The Pilot Node aims to integrate METROFOOD-RI's services and datasets with the EOSC ecosystem, leveraging EOSC Core services such as AAI, the Discovery Hub, and the Service Catalogue, while also exploring federated service discovery and access through EOSC Exchange mechanisms. The pilot will validate workflows where researchers can discover, access, and process large-scale datasets using EOSC-enabled computing infrastructure and other systems.

A key goal of the METROFOOD-RI pilot is to demonstrate how domain-specific services and datasets can be made interoperable with broader EOSC capabilities, enabling cross-disciplinary research and enhancing the accessibility of food data across Europe.

It also provides a ground for integrating user support functions and resolving data access issues collaboratively across nodes.

From an EOSC integration perspective, the objectives are to integrate EOSC Core services (e.g., AAI, Discovery Hub, Helpdesk) and to ensure that METROFOOD-RI services become visible and actionable through the federated service catalogue. This includes developing lightweight interoperability solutions and exposing relevant METROFOOD-RI services for use in scientific workflows that require high-quality data.

Success in Phase I will be measured by the successful implementation and demonstration of two key Scientific User Stories, involving data discovery, validation, and computing scenarios. Additionally, success includes resolving integration challenges with EOSC Core Services and ensuring that researchers can perform real world studies via the EOSC ecosystem.

3.8.2. Scientific user stories

METROFOOD-RI SUS1: Metabolomic analysis for food quality

Description: As a food chemist, I want to perform metabolomic analysis of food products to evaluate freshness, flavour, and environmental influences on quality, so that I can identify key metabolic markers, assess nutrient variations, and detect potential contaminants.

Researcher perspective:

- Search EOSC Discovery Hub to find food quality services.
- Find the METROFOOD-RI Data Catalogue, which provides metabolic profiles related to freshness, flavor, and nutritional composition.
- Log in using EOSC AAI to access the catalogue.
- Submit a request for the metabolomic analysis for food quality service, which is processed via the METROFOOD-RI Helpdesk.
- Realize that local computational resources are insufficient for the scale of statistical and machine learning analysis needed.
- With the support of the METROFOOD-RI Helpdesk, find suitable services such as EGI Cloud Compute.
- Search the Discovery Hub to select appropriate EGI cloud computing service.
- Request and gain access to the identified cloud infrastructure for data processing.
- Run analyses to evaluate nutrient differences and contamination patterns.

Related Nodes: EGI, Sandbox

EOSC Services: AAI, Service Catalogue, Discovery Hub, METROFOOD-RI Data Catalogue, Helpdesk

Figure 8: METROFOOD-RI SUS1 flow diagram

METROFOOD-RI -SUS2: Linking nutrition and socio-economic data for food policy

Description: As a researcher, I want to combine food composition and consumption data with socio-economic indicators across European regions, so I can better understand disparities in dietary quality and support evidence-based food policies.

Researcher perspective:

- Search METROFOOD-RI data catalogues to find nutritional composition and food consumption data of commonly consumed food products across various European regions.
- Use the same credentials via EOSC AAI to log into the EOSC Discovery Hub and search for socio-economic datasets, such as income levels, education, and household expenditure.
- Identify relevant data sources in CESSDA data catalogue and request access.
- Attempt to combine nutritional/consumption datasets with socio-economic indicators, but face issues due to different metadata structures and variable definitions across infrastructures.
- Submit a support request via the EOSC Helpdesk, which coordinates between METROFOOD-RI and CESSDA support teams to resolve alignment issues.
- Once the issue is resolved, successfully integrate the datasets and run comparative analysis.

Related Nodes: CESSDA, Sandbox

EOSC Services: AAI, Service Catalogue, Resource Discovery Hub, METROFOOD-RI Data Catalogue, Helpdesk

3.8.3. Use and feedback of core services

AAI
<p>Integration status: Done Feedback: EOSC AAI has been successfully implemented within the METROFOOD-RI environment through the deployment of an Infrastructure Proxy, which manages access to the node’s services. In addition, a Community AAI has been set up to support user enrolment, identity linking, and the management of groups and roles.</p>
Helpdesk
<p>Integration status: Done Feedback: Integration was very straightforward, as the Service Owner did most of the work, including creating a proxy to enable two-way integration between the METROFOOD-RI Helpdesk instance and the Sandbox Helpdesk instance. Additionally, the METROFOOD-RI Helpdesk was successfully integrated with the CESSDA Helpdesk, further improving communication and support coordination between the nodes.</p>
Monitoring
<p>Integration status: In progress Feedback: Integration was very quick and straightforward. The Service Owner handled most of the work, we just needed to confirm our URL addresses. Additional requirements: Confirm our URL addresses once all work is completed.</p>
Service catalogue
<p>Integration status: Done Feedback: We have completed mapping the METROFOOD service properties to the EOSC requirements and successfully integrated the METROFOOD production services into the EOSC Discovery Hub via REST API.</p>

Table 12: METROFOOD-RI use of core services

3.8.4. METROFOOD-RI Pilot Node exchange services

METROFOOD-RI Data Catalogues
<p>METROFOOD-RI Data Catalogues used in SUS1 and SUS2 provide access to a wide range of resources, including datasets, services, training materials, tools, and software related to food quality, safety, and metrology. Content is contributed by institutions across 14 European countries and supports multidisciplinary research in food science, agriculture, chemistry, and environmental biotechnology.</p> <p>The catalogues follow FAIR principles and are being integrated with EOSC Core services such as AAI, Discovery Hub, Helpdesk or Service Monitoring. Integration plans include real-time synchronization of catalogue records and programmatic access through REST APIs. A pilot implementation of FoodCASE as a domain-specific repository is also in progress. More information and a link to the service can be found here.</p>
RM-App (Reference Materials Application)
<p>The RM-App is a user-friendly tool designed to help researchers and professionals in the agrifood sector identify appropriate Reference Materials (RMs) for testing and calibration. Users can search by parameter, matrix type, or matrix–analyte combinations, with RMs organized into classes such as complex matrix RMs and pure substances.</p> <p>The app supports testing accuracy, regulatory compliance, and operational efficiency by reducing the risk of using incorrect materials. It is widely used by research laboratories, food safety authorities, academic institutions, and agrifood manufacturers. More information and a link to the service can be found at RM App.</p>
Search & Compare App
<p>The Search & Compare App is designed to support research and professionals in retrieving and comparing food-related data across multiple FoodCASE databases. Users can perform a basic search (e.g. entering a product name) or apply advanced filters (e.g. specifying component values) to refine results.</p> <p>The app queries selected databases in parallel and returns harmonized information, including product names, synonyms, and detailed composition data. This functionality allows users to quickly identify and compare data across different sources, improving research efficiency, transparency, and reproducibility.</p>

Table 13: METROFOOD-RI Exchange services

3.8.5. Cross-node integration and federation aspects

SUS1 relies on the METROFOOD-RI Data Catalogue being federated with the EOSC Discovery Hub, and on the interoperability of computational services provided by EGI. As a result, the scientist can search and discover harmonized food composition datasets and seamlessly integrate them with EOSC Cloud resources for large-scale analysis.

Federation was tested through the EOSC AAI Single Sign-On, which allowed researchers to authenticate once and gain access both to METROFOOD-RI data catalogue, EOSC Discovery Hub and EGI's cloud computing infrastructure. This is of benefit to researchers, as they can easily combine distributed datasets with computational power, and for METROFOOD-RI/EGI as it exposes their resources to a wider range of community.

SUS2 relies on federation of the METROFOOD-RI Data Catalogue with the CESSDA Data Catalogue through the EOSC Helpdesk. As a result, researchers could not only discover nutritional and consumption datasets from METROFOOD-RI and socio-economic datasets from CESSDA via the EOSC Discovery Hub but also rely on cross-node support mechanisms when issues occurred. Federation was tested through AAI interoperability and data flow integration between the Discovery Hub, Helpdesk, and both the CESSDA and the METROFOOD-RI catalogues. This proved useful to researchers, as it enabled integration of datasets across different scientific domains, and to METROFOOD-RI/CESSDA as it demonstrated their ability to deliver data catalogues across federated EOSC infrastructures.

The METROFOOD-RI Infrastructure Proxy has also been connected with external Community AAls affiliated with other pilot nodes, to enable cross-node authentication.

3.8.6. Technical implementation status, challenges and solutions

The technical implementation of the METROFOOD-RI node within EOSC Beyond has focused on achieving federation with the EOSC Sandbox service Catalogue, enabling AAI integration, using the EGI Cloud environment for large-scale analysis, and integrating Monitoring Service and Helpdesk to ensure cross-node support mechanisms and availability of METROFOOD-RI resources. By M18, METROFOOD-RI has successfully registered as an EOSC provider, exposed both Data Catalogue and Reference Material App as federated services, and tested access through the EOSC Discovery Hub. EOSC AAI has been implemented into both the Data Catalogue and the RM-App. As part of this work, the METROFOOD-RI Infrastructure Proxy was deployed to act as a single point of entry to the METROFOOD-RI node's services, while the Community AAI enables advanced community management functions such as group and role administration.

These components also facilitate the federation of METROFOOD-RI with external community AAls affiliated with other pilot nodes. The EOSC Helpdesk and the CESSDA Helpdesk integration have also been implemented successfully. In the next phase, the Monitoring Service will be deployed and prepared for final adjustments. Furthermore, work will focus on integrating the Search & Compare App and enabling dataset harvesting from OpenAIRE via OAI-PMH.

Challenges encountered included differences in metadata schemas between the METROFOOD-RI catalogue and EOSC requirements, which could affect dataset discovery. This was resolved by implementing mappings to align food-specific metadata to EOSC standards. Aside from this, no major issues have been identified, and regular

meetings with technical teams from the service providers have ensured smooth and steady progress in the integration process.

3.9. NFDI

3.9.1. Node Profile and integration goals

The NFDI Pilot Node is serving as a technical integration platform for the emerging NFDI candidate node in the EOSC Federation of Nodes. It is a connection point between the “Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur e.V.” (NFDI, national research data infrastructure) and some of the IT departments of its participating institutions. The NFDI pilot node’s focus is to gather experience in “federating the federation” since NFDI services are deployed in a federated fashion themselves. All of them are provided by the NFDI’s member institutions in a bottom-up fashion and cater mainly to the German research ecosystem providing means to treat research data as a common good.

The overarching goal with respect to EOSC is to explore technical possibilities in connecting Core and exchange services to complete the portfolio and usefulness of NFDI services by adopting connectivity to the wider research landscape in Europe.

A successful Pilot Node phase leaves extensive experience with the practitioners that are building the NFDI candidate Node in parallel to the Pilot Node. Knowledge transfer from the EOSC Beyond sandbox to the larger operational infrastructures is one of the main goals of this effort.

3.9.2. Scientific user stories

Title: Data discovery and infrastructure use across nodes (NFDI-SUS-1)

As a researcher from a research institution in Europe I want to make use of data I find in the (meta-)data catalogue provided by NFDI. Ideally, I can explore it without having to download a potentially large dataset onto my own laptop in order to assess its use for my purpose. In this endeavour I choose from a list of computing service providers in a different Node (i.e. EGI), make use of their infrastructure, transfer the data from the NFDI catalogue there and analyse it. I could even publish any results from my efforts back in the NFDI catalogue and thus enhance the existing data with new findings and make it even more useful.

Figure 9: NFDI-SUS-1 flow diagram

3.9.3. Use and feedback of core services

AAI
Status: Done
<p>The NFDI pilot node brings their own AARC-compliant AAI with different community and infrastructure proxies so users can login to different services with their home institution's credentials. Integrating the Sandbox AAI has been straightforward because of the common base in AARC-compliance. The AAI integration is considered done.</p>
Discovery Hub
Status: Done
<p>Integration with the Service Catalogue provided by the EOSC Sandbox to make services available in the User Space was easy and doable in under 1 hour total time. Registering a provider and services afterwards was almost self-explanatory and successful with minor feedback from the catalogue team. For evaluation and testing purposes, the Whitelabel User Space provided by Cyfronet was also deployed on a kubernetes cluster at DESY with some help from the developers. Services have been onboarded initially but some details in its operation are still to be worked out and adapted. It will later be used for testing the federation of catalogues between the nodes. The integration with the Front Office provided by the sandbox is done while the local deployment is still in progress.</p>
Helpdesk

Status: In progress

The NFDI pilot node is striving to have a tenant in the existing helpdesk system provided in the sandbox. This is work in progress.

Table 14: NFDI use of core services

3.9.4. NFDI Pilot Node exchange services

The NFDI node currently offers a **metadata catalogue** for dataset publications as an exchange service to their own and all external users. It hosts metadata about datasets and their storage location and also serves as a platform for minting DOIs for sets of stored and published datasets. A landing page and an ingestion UI with corresponding metadata schema registry as well as a storage service that holds the datasets themselves complete the offer. The information about the datasets is available in a web-based UI as well as an HTTP-based REST-API for use with scripts or other web services. Scientific communities can make use of the catalogue free of charge given that they provide a metadata schema and the personnel to curate the data they want to store. Integration with the EOSC Beyond Sandbox AAI ensures authenticated dataset uploads while downloads of published datasets can be completed anonymously.

3.9.5. Cross-node integration and federation aspects

Together with the EGI node and the University Polytechnica de Valencia (UPV) it was shown that the integration between the public data catalogue and the compute service of EGI used via UPV's infrastructure manager is possible by establishing a method for machine-actionable access to datasets directly from the DOI resolver. For this effort, an extension of the landing page service hosted by DESY was developed that makes use of the metalink standard in providing information about data locality. During the integration it became evident that direct dataset access from DOIs by making it machine-actionable is a valuable addition to dataset repositories because it renders them more interoperable than by only providing human-actionable access to datasets and makes data workflows run independent of intermittent user actions. This is especially useful when dealing with large datasets that need to be transferred between infrastructures and cannot be downloaded to a user's machine due to their size or due to the number of different datasets which need automated workflows in order to achieve the desired outcomes in a reasonable amount of time.

Service	Role	Information
Public data catalogue	provider	https://public-data.desy.de
EGI compute service	provider	https://www.egi.eu/service/cloud-compute/
Infrastructure manager	provider	https://im.egi.eu/im-dashboard/

Table 15: NFDI-SUS-1 cross-node service usage

3.9.6. Technical implementation status, challenges and solutions

Until M18, several integrations with Core services have been completed, such as AAI integration, onboarding of a service in the Sandbox service catalogue to make it available in the User Space. Integrations with the central helpdesk and monitoring services are still work in progress but will be completed in due time.

For the inter-node use case demonstrated during the project, the implementation of the direct dataset access mechanism by providing a metalink-formatted XML-according to **RFC5854** making use of content negotiation for the landing page of the public data catalogue at DESY was as crucial as the implementation of its client-side parsing with **dataHugger** by Miguel Caballier (UPV). These two complementary efforts enabled machine-actionable dataset access by only providing a DOI to dataHugger and letting it download the requested datasets to a dynamically created compute cluster without further user interaction.

In the upcoming period, M18 and beyond, two additional exchange services are planned to be added to the NFDI pilot node. Kadi4Mat, a virtual research environment originated in the materials science domain and combines a data repository with an electronic laboratory notebook (ELN). Secondly, an instance of Invenio, being enrolled in the NFDI candidate node, will use the EOSC Beyond sandbox to gain expertise using the interoperability features offered in EOSC Beyond. Also it is foreseen to further the integration of the User Space provided in the EOSC Beyond Sandbox with the node's own marketplace as well as the integration between data sources and the knowledge graph.

3.10. NI4OS-Europe

3.10.1. Node Profile and integration goals

NI4OS-Europe is the research community in Southeast Europe that took part in the NI4OS-Europe project to help develop and integrate national Open Science Cloud initiatives in 15 Member States and Associated Countries. Over the project's lifetime, we set up national-level initiatives, rolled out Core services, and created EOSC onboarding procedures for regional services and repositories. As a result, we successfully brought 46 repositories, 35 thematic services, 22 generic services, and 8 core services into the EOSC federation during the project's duration.

Our main integration goal is to upgrade and redeploy our Core services, along with their related interfaces and onboarding processes, to bring them in line with the latest developments in EOSC. This will make our systems more resilient, flexible, and compatible with the changing EOSC ecosystem, ultimately supporting long-term usability and integration.

NI4OS-Europe Pilot Node main goal is to unite regional services and repositories that matter most to research communities in Climate Science, Life Science, Digital Cultural

Heritage, and Computational Physics. Since these communities are the largest in the area, we began by focusing on them, but we're also willing to support other regional research communities. The thematic services we bring together usually tap into the regional generic services, such as computational and storage resources, which are also featured in our catalog. Furthermore, we have a set of core services that monitor the performance of all our thematic and generic services and repositories. Overall, our catalog covers repositories, thematic services, generic services, and core services.

Our core objectives drive this mission forward. We champion the widespread adoption of FAIR principles for data management and actively provide technical and policy support to help service providers make their offerings available through the EOSC Portal. A fundamental part of our strategy is to support the establishment and development of National Open Science Cloud Initiatives (NOSCI) in each of the 15 participating countries, ensuring that the countries in Southeast Europe are well-represented and active participants in the EOSC governance and service landscape.

Ultimately, success for a NI4OS-Europe pilot is measured by the tangible integration and adoption of Open Science practices and services. This is visible through the successful integration of a diverse range of services and resources from the region into the EOSC catalogue, making them discoverable and accessible to the wider European research community. Success is also marked by a demonstrable increase in the application of FAIR principles to research data within participating scientific communities and repositories. The establishment of self-sustaining National Open Science Cloud Initiatives that continue to promote Open Science long after the project's lifetime, coupled with strong engagement from regional research communities who actively use the onboarded services, are the final markers of a successful endeavour.

More practically, within the EOSC Beyond framework, we're working to smoothly transition from the old core service layer to the new one provided by EOSC Beyond, including all its features and components.

3.10.2. Scientific user stories

NI4OS-SUS-1: Comparative analysis using services from various countries to create a new simulation model

At the outset of the project, we pinpointed four key user stories, one for each user community, which we summarized as follows:

- As a regional LifeScience user, I want to leverage the drug discovery and molecular dynamics services from the NI4OS Europe catalogue to run simulations using their cloud resources.
- As a regional Climate researcher, I aim to utilize the available thematic services for climate research, along with the deposited datasets, to explore new climate models on the cloud services provided by NI4OS-Europe.
- As a regional digital cultural heritage user, I need access to the datasets in the NI4OS-Europe repositories, as well as DCH tools, to develop new models and simulations.

- As a regional scientist, I plan to conduct a comparative analysis using data from various countries to create a new simulation model.
- Meanwhile, we realized it could be possible to combine all these stories into a single, more comprehensive one that covers every step in each. We pinpointed the key steps of such a story as:
- Simulation development – our first step sets up a development environment where researchers can create a simulation of interest. For instance, they can use **PARADOX cluster** for simulations written in lower-level languages or **FINKI Cloud** for high-level languages. They also get access to our **IPB code repository service**, which allows them to commit their in-progress code and test the latest version locally.
- Input dataset preparation – in this step, researchers prepare the input dataset to be used in the simulation. The requirements for this step vary depending on the type of simulation and may involve using an external service, such as **Gaussian API** or **Schrödinger API**, for input dataset creation, or retrieving the dataset from a repository like the **NI4OS-Europe repository service**.
- Simulation configuration preparation involves setting up the config file that will be submitted with the simulation. This file determines how the simulation is initialized. The complexity of the simulation might decide whether we generate the config file using an external service.
- Testing and benchmarking – in this step, the researcher can test the simulation in a production-like environment. A small amount of HPC or cloud resources is needed for this step.
- Production runs – once testing is complete, the researcher gains access to the HPC resource to run a full simulation and store the resulting datasets.
- Analysis of the results – in this last step of the user story, researchers access the Cloud resource from which they can retrieve datasets obtained in the previous step and analyze the results in the provided development environment.

Figure 10: NI4OS-SUS-1 flow diagram

3.10.3. Use and feedback of core services

AAI
<p>Status: Done</p> <p>We have successfully rolled out the NI4OS-Europe Federation Registry, offering a secure web interface where service operators can register their OpenID Connect and SAML-based services. Using the federation registry user interface is easy to understand, and adding a new service to the registry is straightforward and clearly explained.</p>
Helpdesk
<p>Status: Done</p> <p>We've set up a Zammad-based Helpdesk system for NI4OS-Europe and fully integrated it with the AAI. It's possible to configure the entire setup from the Zammad helpdesk's web-based user interface. However, there are many parameters to configure to get the desired helpdesk setup. We also haven't tested how the instance would transition to another server, so it's possible that all parameters would need to be set up again manually after the transition.</p>
Service Catalogue
<p>Status: Done</p> <p>We have deployed the vanilla EOSC catalogue as a NI4OS-Europe resource catalogue. It wasn't easy, but we managed to get it done. The process involves a lot of requirements and configuration steps. We're now developing installation guidelines to help with deploying other nodes. We've also integrated the catalogue with AAI.</p>

Table 15: NI4OS-Europe use of core services

3.10.4. NI4OS Pilot Node exchange services

Our goal is to deploy NI4OS-Europe instances of all core services where possible. Since this process takes time, we also onboarded the resource to the EOSC Beyond sandbox instances of the core service alongside deployment to familiarize ourselves with the core service APIs. Our aim was to onboard at least a set of services mentioned in our use case. So, we onboarded the following set of services into the EOSC Beyond sandbox:

- **PARADOX cluster**
- **FINKI Cloud**
- **IPB Code repository service**
- **Gaussian API service**
- **Schrödinger API service**

- [NI4OS-Europe repository service](#)

These services are available through the sandbox, and researchers can access them for testing purposes, following the procedures and access policies outlined during onboarding.

3.10.5. Cross-node integration and federation aspects

NI4OS-Europe AAI is now integrated with the AAI of other EOSC Beyond pilot nodes. As a result, services listed in the NI4OS-Europe catalogue can be accessed by researchers from other pilot nodes, enabling them to authenticate with their institutional credentials. We tested this integration with the NI4OS-Europe core services. Working with other pilot nodes, we successfully verified the workflow of ticket creation within the Helpdesk system.

3.10.6. Technical implementation status, challenges and solutions

Deploying the NI4OS-Europe node is on track with the integration timeline we set at the start of the project. We began the integration process with the service catalogue deployment and followed up with the helpdesk deployment. Then, we successfully connected these two services, allowing researchers to use the helpdesk immediately, without any account approval or intervention from the helpdesk administration team.

To speed up the onboarding of resources that are already verified and tested, we used the EOSC Beyond sandbox catalogue instance. We basically prepared service descriptions as JSON files and used the API to register them in the catalogue. This was crucial not only for testing the catalogue API but also for streamlining the registration process in the NI4OS-Europe catalogue, as we can reuse the same JSON files to register services in the NI4OS-Europe instance.

Our next major milestone was deploying the service catalogue. We utilized the vanilla EOSC Beyond services catalogue and, with the development team's support, set up the catalogue instance for NI4OS-Europe purposes. This core service was also integrated with the AAI, making it accessible to researchers from other pilot nodes.

4. Challenges and lessons learned

4.1. Feedback from the Pilot Nodes

The first eighteen months of integration show that the effective network of cooperating nodes is less a single switch and more a chain of small, practical decisions that either accelerate the next step or quietly slow it down. The following section outlines the main challenges encountered, their underlying causes, the ways in which pilots addressed them, and the patterns identified for the next phase.

4.1.1. Identity and access

AAI integration turned out to be the most critical dependency in almost every use case. Nodes that had their AAI integration completed early, such as CESSDA, LifeWatch ERIC, and METROFOOD-RI, were able to progress quickly with federated access to catalogues, helpdesks and cloud resources. Their researchers could log in once and move across nodes without barriers.

Other nodes faced difficulties. For example, INSTRUCT-ERIC struggled with Keycloak version limitations that blocked proper attribute mapping. CNB-CSIC needed time to set up a dedicated proxy domain before its validation service could connect. These cases delayed other planned integrations because AAI is always the entry point for a researcher.

Why this matters: without reliable AAI, other services cannot be tested or adopted. Every obstacle in login creates extra effort for both researchers and support teams.

Lesson: AAI should be the first integration step for any node. Supported versions need to be clear and stable across the project. Where local systems are outdated, a proxy-based solution should be offered to avoid blocking progress.

4.1.2. Onboarding and catalogues

Many pilots highlighted the problem of duplicated service onboarding. A service registered once in one catalogue was not automatically visible elsewhere. This forced service providers to repeat onboarding steps, wasting time and creating inconsistencies. LifeWatch ERIC and METROFOOD-RI addressed this by aligning their metadata with EOSC requirements. They produced mappings and transformations to ensure their catalogues could be harvested by the EOSC Service Catalogue and Discovery Hub. NFDI and CESSDA went further and tested a White-label Front Office locally to explore how catalogue federation could work in practice.

Why this matters: duplicated onboarding increases maintenance costs and slows down federation. Inconsistent metadata also makes services harder to discover for researchers.

Lesson: service onboarding should be a *register once, see everywhere* process. EOSC Beyond Technical Roadmap has taken this requirement onboard to provide a solution for a truly Federated Service Catalogue. Metadata mappings should be disseminated and easily accessed as reusable artefacts so other nodes facing the same issue can reuse the work.

4.1.3. Helpdesk integration

Several pilots successfully connected their helpdesks with the EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox one. CESSDA and METROFOOD-RI established cross-tenant routing, which allowed support requests to be passed between nodes. This was important in cases where user stories crossed disciplines, such as combining food composition data with socio-economic datasets.

At the same time, concerns appeared once real tickets started to cross organisational boundaries. INSTRUCT-ERIC raised sustainability and privacy questions, especially about how long user data should be stored and who should own a ticket once it leaves its original tenant.

Why this matters: user support is a key part of the federation experience. If tickets are not routed reliably or data protection rules are unclear, trust in the system decreases.

Lesson: helpdesk federation needs clear rules. Ownership, escalation paths, and data retention periods should be agreed at federation level.

4.1.4. Deployment and operations

The pilots showed that deployment is often the easiest part. For example, CNB-CSIC containerised its Validation Report Service and deployed it on two different cloud providers using the Infrastructure Manager. The process was smooth and quick.

Operational challenges emerged afterwards. Cloud providers sometimes faced capacity limits, as reported by CNB-CSIC at CESNET. Monitoring services were integrated by several pilots, but in most cases alerting rules and escalation paths were still missing. This means that while services were technically monitored, no clear procedure was in place for what should happen when problems occurred.

Why this matters: without clear operational guidelines, services may work during a demonstration but fail under sustained use. Researchers depend on reliability, not just availability.

Lesson: Deployment should always be followed by operational agreements. SLOs, SLAs, monitoring thresholds, alert routing and escalation procedures need to be defined early.

4.1.5. Data movement

Data transfer between infrastructures is a recurring challenge. Large datasets cannot be easily downloaded to a researcher's laptop and re-uploaded elsewhere. Manual transfers are fragile and time-consuming.

The NFDI pilot developed a practical solution using machine-actionable DOIs. By adding metalink information and content negotiation, datasets could be resolved directly into automated transfer instructions. This allowed data to be staged into compute environments without manual intervention. CNB-CSIC also plans to rely on Data Transfer services for moving cryo-EM data to compute clusters, though the exact protocols are still being finalised.

Why this matters: research increasingly depends on large datasets. If data cannot be moved efficiently and securely, scientific workflows break down.

Lesson: data access should be machine-actionable and close to compute resources. Automated transfer protocols with integrity checks are essential. Order Management should also be connected to data staging so provisioning and transfer happen in one step.

4.1.6. Metadata and semantics

Metadata mismatches slow down many integrations. LifeWatch ERIC had to transform its EML metadata into OpenAIRE-compliant format to enable harvesting. METROFOOD-RI faced similar work aligning food-specific metadata to EOSC standards. In joint user stories such as METROFOOD-RI and CESSDA, socio-economic and nutritional datasets could only be integrated after harmonising variable definitions.

Why this matters: without aligned metadata, services and datasets may technically exist in the federation but remain undiscoverable or unusable.

Lesson: schema mappings and controlled vocabularies should be managed as shared, open assets. Making them available through the adapters allows other nodes to reuse them instead of repeating the same work.

4.1.7. Persistent identifiers

PID practices varied widely. CNB-CSIC planned to mint DOIs for validation reports, INSTRUCT-ERIC used OneData handle, and CESSDA and NFDI already mint DOIs for datasets. However, each pilot applied different rules about what gets a PID, how updates are handled, and which metadata is mandatory.

Why this matters: without a shared policy, PIDs lose reliability. Researchers may face inconsistent practices when citing or reusing results.

Lesson: a common PID policy should be defined. This policy should cover the level of granularity (dataset, version, report), rules for updates and new PIDs, and minimum provenance information.

4.1.8. Cross-node use cases

The most compelling results came from cross-node collaborations:

- CESSDA and INSTRUCT-ERIC demonstrated how social scientists could discover and book structural biology instruments with SSO.
- METROFOOD-RI and CESSDA combined food composition and socio-economic data with helpdesk mediation.
- INSTRUCT-ERIC and EGI showed how storage brokering at the point of experiment could support long-term data retention.
- NFDI , LifeWatch and EGI enabled compute close to data by staging datasets via machine-actionable DOIs.
- ENES and EGI demonstrated advanced computational and machine learning environments supported by AAI cross-node federation.
- CNB-CSIB exploited the computational resources offered by the e-INFRA CZ Node to simplify complex validation workflows
- NI4OS-Europe exploited the capabilities of the EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox by deploying a dedicated instance of the Service Catalogue which provides out of the box interoperability with the Service Catalogue Sandbox instance.

Why this matters: These user stories show real scientific added value from the integration between Pilot Nodes. They demonstrate workflows that no single Node could provide alone.

Lesson: User stories should always be the basis to test and experiment the validity of the Pilot Federation across a set of Nodes. This ensures the network of the nodes is tested in realistic scenarios.

4.2. Recommendations for next phase

Taken together, the pilot experiences show that integration between Nodes within the future federation is achievable but requires discipline in execution. Success depends on treating AAI as the first step, avoiding duplicated onboarding, investing in metadata alignment, and testing real cross-node workflows. Sustainability, documentation, and measurable criteria are equally important to move beyond demonstrations and into operational reality.

From the challenges and experiences observed across the Pilot Nodes, several overall recommendations can be drawn to guide the next phase of integration:

Prioritise foundations before expansion. Core enablers such as AAI, federated catalogue and helpdesk interoperability should be completed and stabilised before additional services or advanced workflows are added.

Promote *integrations by design*. Development of use cases should go in ways that involve more than one node, ensuring that identity, data, and service flows are tested across boundaries rather than within isolated infrastructures.

Treat documentation and mappings as shared infrastructure. Onboarding guides, metadata transformations, and schema alignments should be produced once and reused widely. This reduces duplication and provides consistent experiences for both researchers and providers.

- Balance technical delivery with sustainability. Each service integrated into the federation should have a clear owner, support model, and long-term outlook beyond the project, to avoid reliance on short-term effort from individual service teams.
- Adopt an integrate-once AAI federation hub (with a multi-hub fallback) to reduce bilateral proxy setups and standardise entitlement mapping across pilots.
- Pilot catalogue federation & synchronisation so the Discovery Hub can surface selected services from other nodes by default, while the User Space supports entitlement-aware ordering and Node-level curation.

5. Conclusions and next steps

This report summarises the journey and achievements of the EOSC Beyond network of Pilot Nodes. The pilots have provided clear evidence that complex scientific problems benefit immensely from a diverse, cross-disciplinary set of resources. These resources, when delivered in conjunction by a federation of Pilot Nodes, enable solutions that would be impossible to achieve within a single disciplinary or infrastructure silo.

Emerging patterns from scientific user stories are starting to reveal which Node-to-Node interconnections are most beneficial for delivering integrated research environments. The pilots have explored some of these patterns and its benefits, which include:

Coupling of e-Infrastructure and Thematic Nodes: Thematic Nodes typically benefit from infrastructure-oriented resources such as the computational, storage and analytical environments needed to exploit domain specific resources. Nodes with infrastructure-rich resources such as EGI, e-INFRA CZ have come together nicely with Thematic Nodes such as ENES, LifeWatch, MetroFood and INSTRUCT

Cross-Domain Data Interoperability: Cross-domain scientific challenges require the analysis of datasets from different disciplines. In such cases, enabling discoverability and accessibility of these datasets through catalogue interoperability, remains a significant challenge. Pilots, including MetroFood and LifeWatch have begun experimenting with cross-catalogue mappings among domain specific formats. These mappings should evolve into community adaptors when further communities can benefit from them.

Simplified scientific workflows set up: User stories involving complex scientific workflows require an advanced technical set up that includes the right infrastructure coupled with datasets, services and analytical environments. Orchestration services, such as the Deployment Service in EOSC Beyond are key to automating these complex setups that typically require advanced technical skills. Pilots such as CNB-CSIC, Lifewatch and NFDI have demonstrated complex orchestration of resources across Nodes.

Reproducibility of scientific simulations/workflows: User stories have proven the need to recreate complex simulation environments to validate previous experiments or simulate specific laboratory conditions prior to physical experiments. Pilots such as NI4OS, have proven the benefit to offer integrated environments to perform complex simulations. This requires publicly available code repositories for the discovery of models together with access to HPC facilities.

The next phase of the project will further explore these patterns that empower scientists to utilize resources across the federation. Pilots will evolve in parallel with the Core and innovation services that are being developed as part of the EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox, which provides the essential components for federating the Pilot Nodes. Test and validation plans will be formulated. These plans will guarantee that the Pilots not only deliver a set of integrated technical building blocks but also enhance the scientific value to the broader federation.

A key conclusion from this phase is that a truly successful pilot federation must hide the inherent complexities of the federated infrastructure from the end user. The user experience should be as simple and intuitive as possible, allowing them to treat the federation as a single, unified research environment.

Acronyms

Term	Definition
AAI	Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure
AMS	ARGO Messaging Service
API	Application Programming Interface
ARIA	Cloud platform for Access and Facility management
B2B	Business to Business
B2C	Business to Consumer
CESSDA	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives
CERN	European Organization for Nuclear Research
CLARIN	Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure
CMCC	Euro-Mediterranean Center on Climate Change
CNB-CSIC	National Biotechnology Center Spanish National Research Council
CYFRONET	Academic Computer Centre Cyfronet AGH
DARIAH	Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EB	EOSC Beyond
ENES	European Network for Earth System Modelling
ENVRI	Environmental Research Infrastructures
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GRNET	Greek Research and Technology Network
KIT	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology
LW	LifeWatch
METROFOOD-RI	Infrastructure for promoting Metrology in Food and Nutrition
NFDI	German National Research Data Infrastructure
NI4OS	National Initiatives for Open Science in Europe
OSCARs	Open Science Clusters' Action for Research and Society
PID	Persistent Identifier

Term	Definition
RI	Research Infrastructure
SSHOC	Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud
SLA	Service Level Agreement
TCB	Technical Coordination Board
VRE	Virtual Research Environments
VR	Virtual Reality

Table 16: Acronyms

6. Appendix

This appendix presents the five standard templates used during the Kraków workshop (March 2025). Each was completed by the Pilot Nodes and provided the concrete context and inputs that underpin the integrations reported in this deliverable. The materials included are: the User Story Technical Analysis, the Core Service Requirement Sheet, the EOSC Federation Discovery Journey Map – provider perspective, the EOSC Federation Discovery Journey Map – user perspective, and the Integration Roadmap. Together, these filled artefacts connect real user needs to actionable technical work, ensure consistency across nodes, and keep the integration process transparent and traceable.

6.1. User Story Technical Analysis

In EOSC Beyond Pilot Network the nodes are bringing a set of resources, including services, for the scientific re-use. The Pilot federation, from the user point of view, goal is based on the ability to use these services together. In order to understand which services can be consumed and composed within the network, an integration analysis is required. The analysis assesses what service integrations are needed to enable user stories planned to be supported in the EOSC Beyond Pilot Network. This integration may, in the end, be of a certain logical type depending on the nature/type of resources paired up together.

Exchange resource types included in the integration. Choose from the list

Services:

Research products:

Template for a resource/service integration analysis within the EOSC Federation of Nodes, focusing on identifying necessary integrations to support planned user stories and classifying integration types:

Resource/Service Integration Analysis Template: EOSC Federation of Pilot Nodes

1. Analysis ID: [Unique identifier for this analysis]
2. Analysis Title: [Concise and descriptive title, e.g., "Integration Analysis: Genomics Data Analysis Workflow"]
3. Scope and Focus:
 - User Stories: [List the specific user stories this analysis supports. Provide a brief description of each user story. Link to user story documentation if available.]
 - Nodes Involved: [List the EOSC nodes whose resources are relevant to this analysis. Specify if all relevant nodes are included or a subset.]
4. Resource/Service Inventory:
 - Resource/Service ID: [Unique identifier for each resource or service.]
 - Resource/Service Name: [Descriptive name; e.g., "European Nucleotide Archive (ENA)", "Galaxy Workflow Platform"]
 - Node Provider: [Specify the EOSC node providing the resource or service.]
 - Resource/Service Type: [e.g., Data repository, compute service, workflow management system, authentication service, data transfer service]

- API/Interface Availability: [Specify available APIs and interfaces; e.g., REST API, GraphQL API, command-line interface, file system access]
- Data Formats: [If applicable, list supported data formats.]
- Data Models: [If applicable, list data models used.]

5. Required Integrations:

For each user story, list the required integrations between resources and services. Use the following format for each integration:

- User Story ID: [Link to or reference user story documentation.]
- Source Resource/Service ID: [ID/name from the resource/service inventory table.]
- Target Resource/Service ID: [ID/name from the resource/service inventory table.]
- Integration Type: [Propose the Classification for the integration type; Integration Details: [Describe the specific technical details of the integration; e.g., data transfer protocol, API calls, workflow orchestration steps]
- Data Transformation/Mapping: [Specify if any data transformation or mapping will be needed; e.g., data format conversion, metadata harmonization]
- Authentication/Authorization: [Specify authentication and authorization methods.]
- Security Considerations: [Describe any security considerations or constraints.]

6. Integration Type Classification:

Classify each integration based on the nature of the resources involved and the type of interaction. Use the following categories (expand as needed based on your specific context):

- Data Transfer: Moving data between resources; e.g., transferring data from a repository to a compute service.
- API-Based Interaction: Exchanging information via APIs; e.g., querying a metadata catalogue to discover datasets.
- Workflow Orchestration: Coordinating multiple services to execute a complex workflow; e.g., initiating a data transfer, running an analysis job, and storing the results.
- Authentication/Authorization: Integrating authentication and authorization services to enable secure access to resources; e.g., using federated identity management (AAI) to provide single sign-on across multiple services.
- Service Composition: Combining multiple services to create new functionality; e.g., using a data processing service in conjunction with a visualization service.
- Data Transformation/Mapping: Mapping data between different formats or schemas.
- Metadata Harmonization: Aligning metadata schemas across different resources.

7. Analysis and Findings:

Summarize your findings based on the required integrations. Address the following

- Number of Integrations: Total number of integrations identified.
- Integration Complexity: Assess the complexity of each integration and the potential challenges involved.
- Integration Type Distribution: Analyse the distribution of integration types.
- Interoperability Gaps: Identify any gaps or missing components hindering achieving the planned user stories.
- Recommendations: Based on the findings, propose recommendations for improving the interoperability of resources and services within the EOSC federation.

6.2. Core Service Requirement Sheet

Requirements gathering								Information structuring			Analysis and design	Planning
ID	Channel	Title	Problem to be solved/user need	Related user story	Known constraints	User group(s) benefited	Author's affiliation (Pilot)	Related federating capability	Related core service	External nodes/stakeholders potentially involved	Estimated effort analysis	Estimated delivery/release
No.	WP15 workshop	Short description of the proposed requirement	What problem is the user trying to solve? What does the user need and what will the user achieve when the requirement is met?	Example: I'm a climate scientist. I'm looking for a specific set of data from Africa about the temp distribution in Kenya. I have no idea where to find such data and I NEED IT BADLY	Rules and limitations (e.g., time, resource, funding) that may affect	Who will benefit from the result of the implementation? <i>Researchers Service/Resource Providers Research communities Research projects Private company Founder</i>	Who proposed the requirement? <i>Organization name</i>	Part of the functionality affected by the desired requirement (searching, ordering, backoffice, offers, provider view etc.)	Architectural components affected by the desired requirement	Who will also be affected/take part in the process defined by the desired functionality/requirement? (stakeholders/infrastructures)	LOW MEDIUM/ HIGH	Estimated delivery date for the overarching design concept.
1	WP15 Workshop											
2	WP15 Workshop											
3	WP15 Workshop											
4	WP15 Workshop											
5	WP15 Workshop											
6	WP15 Workshop											
7	WP15 Workshop											

Table 17: Core Service Requirement Sheet

6.3. EOSC Federation Discovery Journey Map – provider perspective

Customer/ User Journey map	AWARENESS	INFORMATION GATHERING	DECISION MAKING	ACCESS REQUEST/USE	COMPOSE RESOURCES TOGETHER
GOALS					
ACTIONS					
"Onboarding tool" (or other type of tool) where the actions take place					
TOUCH POINTS (with WPs or other EOSC Pilots/stakeholders)					
FEELING					
PAIN POINTS					
KEY INSIGHTS & OPPORTUNITIES					
Scope: Federated discovery, access and (re)use of scientific resources (EOSC Exchange) in EOSC Network of Pilot Nodes					
Gaps - Required new developments with development timeline:					
Who (WPs/teams)	What	By when, Owner	List of included onboarding tools from the Pilot		

Table 18: EOSC Federation Discovery Journey Map – provider perspective

6.4. EOSC Federation Discovery Journey Map – user perspective

Try to imagine the user interfaces and features that EOSC users will need to enable federated discovery and access within EOSC. Additionally, please provide input from the perspective of providers/nodes in this document: <https://shorturl.at/f5upA> What steps will they need to take to support the user journeys described below?

Customer/ User Journey map	AWARENESS	INFORMATION GATHERING	DECISION MAKING	ACCESS REQUEST/Use	COMPOSE RESOURCES TOGETHER	USE, AFTER-SALES
GOALS						
ACTIONS						
Which discovery tool is conducting this action (s)						
TOUCH POINTS (with WPs or other EOSC Pilots/stakeholders)						
FEELING						
PAIN POINTS						
KEY INSIGHTS & OPPORTUNITIES						
<i>Concluding Order/access management flow</i>						
<i>PERSISTENCE LAYER IN EOSC Federation (Architecture outline)</i>						
<i>Gaps - Required new developments with development timeline:</i>						
Who (WPs/teams)	What	By when, Owner	List of included discovery tool from the Pilot			

Table 19: EOSC Federation Discovery Journey Map – user perspective

6.5. Integration Roadmap

NODE:																								
Year	2025												2026											
Month	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI	XI	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI	XI
Task Name:																								
Task Description:	no																							
Task Name:																								
Task Description:	yes																							
Task Name:																								
Task Description:	no																							
Task Name:																								
Task Description:	yes																							

Table 20: Integration Roadmap